

Interaction, Focus, Motion: Towards Design Principles for Running and Breathing Guidance Apps

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Author: Mehdi Golbaz

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Salzburg University of Applied Sciences
Paris Lodron University of Salzburg

Assessed by:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Alexander Meschtscherjakov
Department of Artificial Intelligence and Human Interfaces
Human-Computer Interaction Division
Paris Lodron University of Salzburg

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Abstract

The increasing use of mobile devices presents challenges for runners seeking to maintain focus during workouts [15]. This thesis explores the iterative design and refinement of a sound-based breathing guidance app for runners, enhanced by a companion app for personalized customization of the running experience. Informed by in-depth analysis of existing user interview data and human-centered design (HCD) principles [26], this research investigates how customization of rhythm, timing, sound elements, and the integration of music could improve focus, intuitive interaction, and long-term engagement with the breathing guidance app. The design choices are strongly influenced by the recognition of music's motivational role for runners [2]. Grounded in theories of embodied cognition, the findings contribute to the development of interaction design principles prioritizing user personalization, seamless integration of preferred stimuli, and enhanced focus within the unique demands of running.

Keywords: Wearable technology, breathing guidance, sound-based interaction, customization, companion app, user-centered design, embodied cognition, music integration, motivation, distraction

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1 Introduction

The integration of technology into recreational running has become a widespread phenomenon. Many runners, especially those who are younger and less experienced, have discovered the use of apps, sports watches, and activity trackers [27]. This technological shift raises concerns regarding whether these same devices might introduce distractions that could negatively affect a runner's overall experience, such as reducing situational awareness or affecting their running form, even while they offer possible benefits such as motivational support, progress tracking, and access to real-time performance data.

Runners' use of technology varies depending on their individual goals and level of experience. Although more competitive runners may benefit from the advanced data analysis capability available on sports watches, casual runners frequently choose apps for basic tracking features and motivating elements [13]. The differences suggest the potential for distractions brought on by devices may differ depending on the specific technologies and the profile of the runner.

Runners need to be able to focus. It means keeping a watch on their physical movements, being aware of their surroundings for safety, and directing mental energy towards performance objectives. According to a study, attentional focus is crucial, and running efficiency can frequently be increased by concentrating on the surroundings [50]. Considering running-related devices are so common, it's essential to investigate how they might affect various facets of a runner's attention (mental vs. physical, internal vs. external). With this knowledge, we can design running technologies to effectively assist runners without compromising their performance.

It's also important to consider the reasons behind runners' technological use. While some could find devices intrinsically motivating, others might not see the same added value [27]. Numerous studies have investigated the link between frequent app use, emotional connection to the app, and increased brand loyalty [39]. Nevertheless, it is crucial to study the possibility that interference introduced by devices could reduce a runner's intrinsic motivation in the long term.

Given the potential for visual interfaces to cause distraction and cognitive overload, this thesis explores sound-based interactions as a less intrusive alternative. Research suggests that auditory cues can be less distracting than visual ones and may even enhance focus and motivation in specific contexts [18]. Furthermore, this sound-based approach is aligned with the principles of embodied cognition, which emphasize the interconnectedness of cognitive processes with bodily actions and sensory experiences [2]. According to embodied cognition, cognitive processes are deeply rooted in the body's interactions with the world, where physical actions and sensory experiences directly influence how users engage with technology [12]. In the context of this study, embodied cognition provides a theoretical foundation for how motion-based interactions and auditory cues can enhance user focus and interaction with the running app.

By leveraging auditory cues and rhythmic patterns, a sound-based app could offer a more natural and intuitive way for runners to interact with technology, while maintaining focus on their physical activity. The innovation in this study lies in the personalization of breathing rhythms and the use of motion-based controls, offering users a more immersive and tailored experience compared to standard running apps that rely heavily on visual and touch interactions. This thesis investigates the potential of a sound-based breathing guidance app to address the limitations of

existing running technologies and enhance the overall running experience. The decision to refine an existing app, rather than develop a new one, is grounded in the opportunity to build on prior feedback and existing functionality. These refinements aim to provide a more personalized and seamless interaction, tailored to runners' needs and preferences.

In numerous fields, achieving and maintaining focus is essential to maximizing performance and enjoyment. Focus is a multifaceted concept that can be defined as the ability to channel mental energy towards relevant goals while filtering out distractions. Within the realm of running, Bauer, Kratschmar, and Mueller highlighted the powerful impact of focusing on outcomes [5]. They emphasize that runners who consistently focus on training strategies (interval vs. continuous), monitor intensity (often through heart rate and pace tracking), and utilize performance analysis tools see better progress and satisfaction. Furthermore, carefully choosing music that complements the runner's taste, passions, and goals for the workout enhances motivation and increases enjoyment of the activity [20]. These findings highlight the link between focus, improved performance, and a positive emotional state.

While managing playlists and notifications may seriously interfere with focus and reduce endurance performance, runners still enjoy listening to music while working out [45]. Focus can be disturbed even by well-meaning tools. Although useful, the current fitness apps can frustrate runners who have to manage separate breathing exercises and music playlists. Through a sound-based breathing guidance app that emphasises seamless integration and reduces the kinds of disruptions associated with visually-driven apps, this thesis aims to address these concerns. Ease of use and customisation are given top priority in this design, which explores how sound may assist focus more than traditional, screen-based interactions.

Research Goals and Questions

Beyond impacting pace and endurance, these diversions can have a big impact on a runner's motivation and general enjoyment. This thesis investigates how to achieve seamless technological integration to reduce distractions for runners and advance the use of focus-enhancing technology in sports and other performance-based activities.

Utilising the principles of embodied cognition [2] and the potential of pace regulation via music [5], this app aims to improve focus and provide a more immersive experience by synchronising auditory guidance with the runner's physical movements. The design prioritizes user control, drawing inspiration from the motivating and occasionally challenging aspects of beginning and completing a workout [41].

This research investigates the following key questions:

- **RQ1:** How can refinements to a sound-based breathing app prototype (such as user-controlled activation or personalized rhythms) improve runners' focus and perceived ease of use?
- **RQ2:** How does iterative design of a breathing app prototype impact the usability (ease of interaction) and effectiveness (ability to meet intended goals) of various interaction methods (screen, haptic, motion-based)?

- **RQ3:** How can interaction design principles and theories of embodied cognition inform the development of motion-based and hybrid interaction methods for a running context?

RQ3 is positioned as a broader, concluding question because it seeks to synthesize the insights gathered from refining the app and evaluating interaction methods. This question aims to bridge theoretical concepts of embodied cognition with practical design principles for future motion-based and hybrid interaction methods, thereby providing a broader foundation for subsequent iterations of app development.

Guiding Principles and Approach

This thesis employs a design-oriented methodology, utilizing iterative prototyping and user feedback to develop and test an innovative sound-based guidance app for runners, as part of the DiMo project's 'Run and Interact' studies. My role involved conducting the user test and contributing to the iteration of the app's design, with a focus on enhancing the sound-based guidance system. Initial design decisions and areas for refinement were informed by insights gathered from the existing app and its role within the DiMo project. The data collection methods included usability testing, surveys, and interviews, all aimed at assessing the app's effectiveness in reducing distractions, promoting concentration, and improving the overall running experience. This research emphasizes the importance of seamless integration, customization, and embodied interaction principles, with the goal of enhancing our understanding of how technology can foster focus and enjoyment in performance-driven activities.

The study follows a mixed-methods approach, beginning with a literature review (Study One) to establish the theoretical foundations and explore relevant research on sound-based guidance systems and motion-based interactions. This was followed by a user test (Study Two) to gather insights on the current app's interactions. Key methods included motion-capture analysis to refine motion-based controls, usability testing of various interaction methods, and personalization of auditory cues based on user preferences. The findings from the user test informed the iterative prototyping process, ensuring alignment with the theoretical insights and user needs identified in the literature review.

Although Study One focuses on the literature review and Study Two centers on the user test, the actual development of this thesis occurred in reverse order. My initial collaboration in the DiMo project's 'Run and Interact' pilot study guided the formulation of the research questions and the subsequent literature review.

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 (Study One) explores the relevant literature and related work, identifying gaps in existing running technologies and examining how theories of embodied cognition and interaction design can inform the development of motion-based and hybrid interaction methods.
- Chapter 3 (Study Two) focuses on the initial user study conducted to gather insights into the current version of the app, including the evaluation of motion-based controls, sound design, and personalization features. This chapter will detail the methodology, results, and implications for further iterations.
- Chapter 4 (Conceded Findings) presents the findings from Study One and Study Two, synthesizing the results and highlighting key insights derived from the iterative app development process.
- Chapter 5 (Conceptual Design) provides the conceptual design recommendations, building on the findings to propose design solutions for the next iteration of the 'Run and Interact Version 2' app, with a focus on motion-based interactions, auditory cues, and personalization.

2 Study One: Theoretical and Methodological Foundations

2.1 Introduction: The Role of Related Work and Literature Review

This section explores four core research areas: embodied cognition principles (which suggest that cognitive processes are deeply rooted in the body's interactions with the world) [35], the benefits and challenges of auditory feedback and motion-based controls, personalization in running apps, and gaps in understanding the long-term impact of these technologies on performance and motivation. These areas are essential to understanding how current running technologies shape the user experience and inform future design considerations.

The related work and literature review provide a critical foundation for understanding running technologies and the potential of sound-based guidance systems. This review addresses key topics such as device limitations, the role of personalization, embodied interaction, and the impact of sound-based interventions on the overall running experience, particularly in enhancing focus and performance.

By analyzing the existing literature, this study aims to uncover theoretical foundations and design considerations that will guide the development of the "Run and Interact" 2.0 app and other sound-based systems in the running context.

This section aims to address the following research questions:

- What are the key principles of embodied cognition and how can they be applied to the design of running technologies?
- What are the potential benefits and challenges of using auditory feedback and motion-based controls in running apps?
- How can personalization and customization be effectively incorporated into sound-based guidance systems to cater to the diverse needs and preferences of runners?
- What are the existing gaps in the literature regarding the long-term impact of sound-based interventions on running performance, motivation, and adherence?

Each of the research questions guides the analysis of the literature, with subsections focusing on principles of embodied cognition (RQ3), auditory feedback and motion-based controls (RQ2), and personalization strategies (RQ1).

In the following subsections, we will explore key areas of literature that directly address the research questions of this thesis. These areas include the limitations of current running technologies, the benefits and challenges of auditory feedback and motion-based controls, and the role of personalization in enhancing user experience. We will also examine gaps in the literature, particularly in understanding the long-term impact of sound-based guidance systems on performance and motivation.

This section will further outline the research methods used in the literature review, explaining how they informed the study's research questions and methodology. Specifically, the literature

review shaped RQ1 by highlighting how refinements to a sound-based breathing app could improve focus and ease of use. It also provided a foundation for RQ2, which investigates the impact of different interaction methods on usability and effectiveness. Finally, the principles of embodied cognition, explored through the literature, helped formulate RQ3, which focuses on integrating motion-based and hybrid interaction methods in app design.

Insights from the literature will be crucial in refining the design and development of the next version of the "Run and Interact" app, ensuring alignment with theoretical foundations and user needs. Finally, the results of the systematic literature review are presented, summarizing key takeaways and their relevance to future iterations of the app.

2.2 Related Work: Gaps and Opportunities in Running Technology

The related work has identified a significant gap in existing solutions: the absence of running experiences that are both completely uninterrupted and focus-enhancing, particularly in terms of minimizing data-driven distractions. The absence of focus-enhancing running experiences is further highlighted by the diverse needs of runners and the uncertainty surrounding the long-term effects of running apps.

The following subsections examine the limitations of current running technologies, focusing on the challenges posed by screen-based interactions and the potential of embodied interaction to offer more intuitive and user-friendly experiences. I will examine the role of sound-based interventions in enhancing the running experience, considering both the benefits and challenges of auditory feedback and motion-based controls. Additionally, I will investigate alternative interaction methods and emphasize the importance of personalization and iterative design in creating effective and engaging running technologies. Through a critical analysis of existing research and the identification of key gaps and opportunities, this section aims to establish a solid foundation for developing a novel auditory feedback system that addresses the limitations of current technologies and fosters a more seamless, focused, and enjoyable running experience.

2.2.1 Limitations of Current Running Technology: A Critical Review

Mobile applications are popular for promoting physical activity because of their widespread use and personalized features that respond to individual user preferences [54]. Meanwhile, some data illustrates that the world's smartphone usage has grown dramatically in recent years; 2.87 billion users were expected in 2020 alone. In 2017, 45 percent of American runners reported using running apps to track their mileage [55]. The long-term behavioural shift facilitated by app-based therapy is still debatable [52]. Menheere et al. [41] and Janssen et al. [27] stress the significance of understanding individual motivating needs and efficiently using technology to address problems in physical activity mobile applications.

Furthermore, even if wearable-based real-time feedback may reduce the likelihood of injury, researchers have not yet clarified how it would impact motivation and performance [59]. Training enthusiasts now find running applications to be a valuable resource. In his 2024 paper, Borchert [8] highlights the variety of features, target markets, and pricing models available by analyzing nine of the most widely used applications on the BarBend website. Certain other programmes, such as Nike Run Club and Couch to 5K, are designed to accommodate individuals with varying degrees of experience and may provide both free and paid coaching plans [8]. Many of these applications have features that runners can use to stay focused while they're out there. A good example of this is the adjustable auditory signals that Strava offers for pace, distance, and progress updates. Furthermore, applications such as Runkeeper and Couch to 5K design assisted runs to streamline the experience and allow runners to concentrate on their effort [46]. In addition, access to music listening services enables users to construct personalised playlists that adjust to their focus and motivating needs [46].

Despite offering useful features, current apps can still be distracting. Runners may lose focus when receiving notifications during intense segments of their run, or experience cognitive

overload when interpreting real-time pace metrics, leading to disruptions in their stride [51]. Research in cognitive psychology has shown even further how disruptions to tasks, such as those from notifications, can significantly impair attention and working memory [3]. Cognitive overload from the endless stream of performance data may also make it more difficult for a runner to be in the present [31]. Even properly conceived research on wearable-based technology may run into implementation issues, as Van Hooren, Plasqui, and Meijer [59] illustrate, where participant misunderstandings over app settings may have impacted results.

These challenges highlight a significant gap in current running technologies: the lack of solutions that offer completely uninterrupted, focus-enhancing experiences, particularly in minimizing data-driven distractions. This gap is underscored by the diverse needs and preferences of runners [27, 33] and the uncertain long-term impact of running apps on motivation and behavior change [52]. To address these issues, it is crucial to explore innovative approaches that prioritize a seamless running experience. The potential of embodied interaction and sound-based guidance presents a promising avenue for overcoming the limitations of current screen-based interactions and meeting the need for personalized solutions.

Research indicates that individual preferences and motivations significantly impact the effectiveness of running technology. Even though wearable-based real-time feedback could help reduce injuries, it's important to understand the various demands of runners and create experiences that are tailored to them [33]. The app's emphasis on breathwork also aligns with research that indicates sound-based guidance may affect running economy and attentional focus [10].

To optimize the user experience and cater to individual needs, the app places a strong emphasis on customization and user control. This approach may encourage consistent use by developing a feeling of autonomy and motivation. By prioritizing auditory guidance and minimizing visual distractions, the app seeks to create a more immersive and focused running experience, a key factor in fostering enjoyment and promoting continued use. While the app does not primarily focus on traditional real-time feedback, it recognizes the importance of precise data and verified variables in wearables, especially when training intensity rises, as highlighted by Clermont et al.'s (2020) emphasis on the significance of accurate data for competitive runners who rely on performance metrics [13].

Compared to other running applications, this adjustable, sound-based breathing guidance application seeks to significantly reduce distractions and improve runners' focus. The app's focus on direct, supportive guidance through personalized breathwork routines distinguishes it from existing apps that often emphasize performance data alone [28]. Offering customised breathwork exercises based on research, the app aims to increase performance and focus. Optionally pairing the app with a wearable could further optimize focus with real-time heart rate monitoring and, potentially, integrate running technique analysis [28]. To enhance the running experience, the app also addresses obstacles like boredom and lack of progress by incorporating gamification components, progress tracking, and motivational soundscapes [28].

In addition to enhancing focus, the app's integrated breathwork techniques offer potential benefits for runners. Its focus on personalisation and auditory guidance provides a unique approach to improving overall running performance. The app aims to promote focus, reduce distractions, and foster enjoyment. It is driven by studies on breathwork, auditory entrainment, and user

preferences. Current research on wearable technology and motivation ¹ highlights the potential for integrating physiological data, such as heart rate and cadence, to improve focus and performance during running. This focus on using technology to assist runners with their running technique aligns with the need for further research on assistive, technique-focused training interfaces, as highlighted by Jensen and Mueller [28].

Having explored the limitations of current screen-based running technologies, we now turn to alternative interaction methods that address these issues.

2.2.2 Current Running Technologies: Limitations and the Potential for Embodied Interaction.

To overcome the limitations of screen-based interactions, alternative methods aligned with the physical and cognitive demands of running must be explored. The growing prevalence of running apps and wearables underscores the need for interaction designers (UI) to develop interfaces that not only meet functional requirements but also enhance usability during physical activity. In this context, embodied interaction, which emphasizes the integration of cognitive processes with sensory experiences, offers a promising solution for creating more intuitive and user-friendly running technologies.

However, research has shown that using screens during physical activity has several difficulties. Seuter et al. [51] asserted that these interactions increased cognitive exertion and significantly impact walking patterns. People prefer smartwatches over smartglasses because they provide less distraction. Mühlbacher and Sperlich [43] showed that even brief glances at smartwatch displays can modify running biomechanics.

The physical size and design of the device significantly influence its usability [34]. Research by Goudsmit and Vos [23] found that, seasoned runners found visual feedback on a smartphone display to be inconvenient. Based on the findings of multiple studies, it appears that wrist-worn solutions like sports watches may offer greater ease of use for runners. This is in line with the findings of a 2016 study by Kuru [34], in which participants expressed frustration at the difficulties in using touchscreens while running, particularly due to perspiration and hand motion. The complexity of real-world application use can pose challenges for the implementation of even well-designed wearable technology research, as seen by the study by Van Hooren, Plasqui, and Meijer [59], where participant confusion about app settings may have affected the findings.

Research highlights a preference for auditory feedback over visual feedback during running due to its non-invasive nature and potential motivational benefits [22]. Unlike visual feedback, which can be distracting and cumbersome, auditory cues provide targeted, non-intrusive guidance that helps runners maintain focus and improve performance.

Regardless, the question of whether apps can really induce lasting changes in behaviour remains unanswered [52]. This emphasises the importance of considering user motivation and

¹For research on integrating physiological data in wearables for human performance, see: Frontiers Research Topic, "Wearable Technology for Human Performance," *Frontiers in Physiology* (2021), available at <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/20640/wearable-technology-for-human-performance>.

technology use when designing physical activity interventions. While wearable-based real-time feedback shows promise in injury reduction, further research is needed to ascertain its effects on performance and motivation [59].

According to research, using sound-based guidance may help with both psychological states like focus and attention [14] and motor learning and coordination [24]. For this reason, auditory feedback has a lot of promise. Specifically, auditory feedback can enhance the efficiency of running for athletes by offering immediate information regarding step rate and impact forces [7]. This feedback can provide significant advantages to runners. Williams et al.'s 2020 [64] research suggests that biosynchronous music² synchronizing the tempo with the runner's heart rate or cadence, can improve running performance while simultaneously reducing the perceived effort.

In addition to auditory feedback, motion-based control, which includes gestures and interactions based on accelerometers, is an emerging area with potential to improve usability and functionality. In a virtual reality running simulation, Kim and Lee [32] demonstrated the beneficial effects of such controls on motor learning and performance. Goudsmit and Vos [22] investigated motion-based cues in low-fidelity prototypes to improve running technique. Other studies have shown the potential of motion-based control to provide personalized music experiences [63] and remote support for runners [67]. This research highlights the importance of considering both the challenges and opportunities presented by technological advancements in the running domain. By embracing iterative design methodologies that prioritize user feedback and explore various interaction methods, developers can create sound-based guidance systems that are not only effective and functional, but also engaging and motivating, ultimately enhancing the overall running experience.

These limitations of current running technologies highlight the need for a paradigm shift in interface design. The concept of embodied cognition, which emphasizes the interconnectedness of cognitive processes with bodily interactions and sensory experiences, offers a promising framework for addressing these challenges and creating more intuitive and user-friendly running experiences.

2.2.3 Alternative Interaction Methods for Running

The limitations of traditional screen-based interactions during running have spurred research into alternative interaction methods that are more suitable for the physical and contextual demands of the activity. Several studies in the field of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) have explored various approaches to address these challenges. For instance, Lin et al. [37] investigated the potential of on-body tapping as a discreet interaction method that could minimize disruptions during runs. The integration of running apps with smartwatches has also been explored to provide a more convenient and accessible interface for runners, as evidenced by the preference for wrist-worn solutions over smartphone displays observed by Goudsmit and Vos [22]. While research in this area is ongoing, these explorations highlight the potential of alternative interaction methods, such as touch gestures, on-body interactions, and smartwatch

²Biosynchronous music synchronizes with a runner's physiological data, such as heart rate or cadence.

integration, to enhance the usability and user experience of running technologies. The development of such intuitive and seamless interaction techniques could address the limitations of traditional screen-based interactions and contribute to a more embodied and enjoyable running experience.

2.2.4 Sound-Based Interventions: Enhancing Running through Multisensory Feedback

a. Auditory Feedback Challenges in Running App Design

The increasing popularity of running apps and wearables, coupled with the growing demand for personalized fitness experiences, presents a unique challenge for user interface (UI) and interaction designers: how to develop interfaces that are both functional and user-friendly while running. The importance of efficient design in this domain cannot be overstated, as the widespread use of running apps emphasizes the need for effective solutions [55]. However, studies have identified various challenges associated with using screens while running. For instance, Seuter et al. [51] found that these interactions significantly impact walking patterns and increase cognitive load.

Mühlbacher and Sperlich [43] presented evidence showing that even brief glances at smartwatch displays may impact running biomechanics. The size and form of the device also significantly affect its usability. Goudsmit and Vos [22] discovered that experienced runners found visual feedback on a smartphone display inconvenient. It suggests that wrist-worn solutions, like sports watches, could provide an even more comfortable and accessible experience. Kuru [34] found that participants experienced frustration with touchscreen interactions due to sweat and hand movements while running. These results are in line with her findings. Despite advances in wearable technology, real-world application remains challenging due to issues like participant confusion over app settings [59]. This highlights the need for designs that simplify user interaction and enhance usability.

b. Alternative Feedback Modalities and Iterative Design

Although visual feedback is still useful, studies indicate that because auditory feedback is non-invasive and can provide precise targets without requiring visual attention, it may be more accurate for running activities [22]. Real-time feedback on step rate and impact forces from sound-based guidance can also improve the running economy [7]. The integration of motion-based control and auditory feedback can enhance motor learning and performance by utilising gestures and accelerometer data [32]. In addition, this integration has the potential to create more engaging and captivating experiences by incorporating personalized music selections based on the runner's physiological state [63], enabling remote support and encouragement from others [11], and potentially adapting music selections based on heart rate data [11].

Studies of biosynchronous music, which matches tempo to a runner's heart rate or cadence, point to the potential for enhanced performance and decreased perceived effort [64].

The varied user preferences observed in prototype testing underscore the need for iterative design. The literature highlights the diverse user preferences regarding real-time feedback, with some studies suggesting that it can be beneficial and motivating, while others point to potential distractions and discomfort. The variability in user preferences for control mechanisms (automatic vs. manual) and sound customization further emphasizes the need for personalized experiences.

In the context of running, haptic feedback, such as vibrations, can be just as important as auditory feedback for discreetly and non-visually conveying information during embodied interaction. The study conducted by Witte et al. [66] has shown that it is feasible to provide real-time biofeedback during runs. Their findings suggest that vibrotactile feedback (the sensation of touch provided by vibrations), can enhance running technique. Various studies in sports demonstrate that haptic cues possess the capability to offer immediate biofeedback while running, resulting in enhanced technique and performance [40].

The following table summarizes key findings from existing research in areas such as sound-based guidance, motion-based control, biosynchronous music [64], multisensory feedback, and user preferences. These insights are crucial for understanding how these technologies can enhance the running experience, particularly through personalization, real-time feedback, and multisensory integration.

Area of Focus		Key Findings	Key Citations
Sound-Based Guidance	Motivational & Affective Aspects	Music enhances enjoyment, performance, and physiological responses. Personalized music selection crucial for motivation. Sound-based guidance can modulate tempo/genre to improve focus and reduce anxiety. Runners desire engaging and varied soundscapes. Music can improve mood and reduce perceived exertion during exercise.	Terry et al. (2020); Bauer & Kratschmar (2015); Kuperman (n.d.); Kuru (2016); Fritz et al. (2013)
	Auditory Feedback	Auditory feedback preferred over tactile feedback due to non-invasive nature and ability to convey complex information. Improves running economy through real-time feedback on step rate and impact forces. Enhances motor learning and coordination. Can be distracting if not personalized. User preferences vary between automatic and manual control of auditory feedback.	Abboud et al. (2014); Saulyanas et al. (2021); Bigliassi et al. (2019); Haffenberg (2011); Seuter et al. (2017); (P008.t3, P017.t2, P019.t2, P005.t4, P120.t4)
	Biosynchronous Music	Synchronizing music tempo with heart rate or cadence can improve performance and reduce perceived effort. Offers a promising avenue for personalized, real-time feedback during running.	Williams et al. (2020)
Motion-Based Control	Usability and Functionality	Enhances motor learning and performance in virtual reality running simulations. Creates more immersive and interactive experiences. Can be used for personalized music experiences and remote support for runners.	Kim and Lee (2022); Chen et al. (2024); Wozniak et al. (2015); Wijnalda et al. (2005)
Multisensory Feedback	Types and Integration	Combining auditory and visual feedback can enhance motor learning and performance. Haptic feedback shows promise for improving running form. Integrating multiple modalities may require careful consideration of the runner's natural movements.	Schaffert et al. (2019); Witte et al. (2020); Srinivasan and Chen (2019)
User Preferences	Customization and Personalization	Runners have diverse preferences for feedback types, levels of control, and sound customization. Personalized training schedules are important for user engagement. Some users prefer touch-based interactions or smartwatch integration.	Vos et al. (2016); (P005.t4, P008.t3, P017.T2, P019.t2, P120.T4, P019.t3, P123.T4); (P003.t2, P106.T3)
Iterative Design	Importance	Iterative design and user feedback are crucial for developing effective sound-based guidance systems.	Goudsmit & Vos (2021); Van Hooren et al. (2024, 2020); Maertens (2015)

Table 1: Overview of embodied interaction, focus, and sound-based guidance in running research.

2.2.5 The Interplay of Related Work and Research Methodology

The related work presented in this section directly addresses the research questions (RQs) and the focus of this thesis by providing a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of running technology and the potential of sound-based guidance systems. It establishes how the identified limitations and gaps in existing running technologies inform and shape the research questions and objectives, setting the stage for a deeper exploration of relevant literature and theoretical frameworks in the subsequent sections.

The related work highlights limitations such as distractions from visual interfaces and the lack of personalization, which inform:

- RQ1: How refinements and iterative design can improve focus and usability in sound-based breathing apps.
- RQ2: The impact of different interaction methods on usability and effectiveness.

The discussion of embodied cognition and its potential for creating more intuitive and user-friendly running experiences addresses:

- RQ3: How principles of embodied cognition can inform the development of motion-based and hybrid interaction methods.

Additionally, the related work underscores the diverse needs and preferences of runners, emphasizing the importance of personalization and customization in sound-based guidance systems, which aligns with RQ1. The exploration of auditory feedback and motion-based controls further supports RQ2.

Gaps identified in current research, such as the limited understanding of the long-term impact of sound-based interventions on running performance, motivation, and adherence, inform RQ3. This research question seeks to explore the potential of sound-based guidance systems to promote long-term engagement and behavior change.

In summary, the related work presented provides a solid foundation for addressing the research questions and achieving the thesis objectives. It highlights limitations of current running technologies, identifies opportunities for improvement, and offers insights into designing a novel sound-based running guidance system that enhances the running experience through personalization, seamless interaction, and focus. By addressing these research questions and building upon the existing literature, this thesis aims to contribute to the development of innovative and effective sound-based guidance systems that enhance the running experience and promote long-term engagement and positive behavior change in runners.

The following section will build upon this foundation by delving into a comprehensive Literature Review, which will further contextualize the research within the broader academic discourse and theoretical frameworks relevant to the thesis.

2.3 Key Findings from the Literature

The advent of wearable technologies and running apps has brought new opportunities for enhancing the running experience, offering real-time feedback, motivation, and performance tracking. However, these technologies also introduce challenges, such as cognitive overload from visual interfaces and the difficulty of interacting with devices during physical activity. This literature review explores the key findings from research on sound-based guidance systems, embodied cognition, and multisensory interaction to uncover how these elements can be leveraged to design more intuitive, seamless, and personalized running technologies.

The review addresses the potential of sound-based guidance to improve focus and performance, the role of personalization in enhancing user satisfaction, and the importance of motion-based interactions in creating more natural and efficient user experiences. By synthesizing findings from sports science, psychology, and human-computer interaction, the review aims to identify opportunities for improving the design of future running technologies.

2.3.1 Bridging the Gap: The Potential of Sound-Based Running Guidance

Investigating sound, motion, and embodied experience in running offers numerous opportunities for creating cutting-edge technologies that leverage the body's natural capacities to improve running. Embodied cognition concepts combined with iterative design techniques allow developers to build customised and flexible sound-based guidance systems that maximise focus, raise performance, and increase running enjoyment in general. However, the synthesis of existing research and prototype data analysis reveals a complex interplay of factors influencing the design of such systems, which emphasises the need for more study to completely comprehend the complex relationship between motion, focus, and embodiment in real-world running scenarios. This understanding will be crucial for developing and enhancing sound-based guidance systems to meet the various demands and preferences of runners, maximising the potential of technology to improve the running experience.

While running apps and wearables offer various benefits, studies have highlighted the challenges of using traditional screen-based interactions during physical activity. These interactions can negatively impact gait, increase cognitive load, and reduce overall ease of use [51]. The difficulties of using touchscreens while running are further exacerbated by factors such as sweat and hand movement, making interaction even more challenging [34]. Even meticulously planned research can encounter difficulties in execution due to the complexities of actual app usage, as demonstrated in the study conducted by Van Hooren, Plasqui, and Meijer [59], where participant confusion regarding app configurations may have impacted the results. These challenges underscore the need for alternative interaction methods that are more intuitive, user-friendly, and less disruptive to the running experience.

The concept of embodied cognition offers a promising framework for addressing the challenges of traditional screen-based running technologies. By aligning interfaces with users' natural movements and cognitive processes, these systems can potentially reduce cognitive load and improve ease of use [65]. However, while these theoretical benefits are compelling, empiri-

cal evidence supporting their long-term impact on running performance and user satisfaction remains limited.

Further research is necessary to validate these claims in real-world scenarios, where factors such as environmental distractions and individual runner preferences may diminish the effectiveness of embodied interactions. To effectively address users' implicit needs in the context of running, a thorough comprehension of their physical and sensory experience is essential [2].

By integrating various sensory modalities, such as auditory and visual feedback, it is possible to create a more comprehensive and instinctive user experience, which improves the process of acquiring motor skills and enhances performance [49]. Regarding running, this could entail delivering immediate feedback on speed, distance, and other pertinent measurements through auditory signals, which are less intrusive than visual feedback and do not necessitate visual focus [23]. Sound-based guidance can enhance running economy by providing immediate feedback on step rate and impact forces [7].

Natural gestures can also improve interactions when incorporated into interface design [6]. Goudsmit and Vos [22] explored the use of basic hand gestures or body movements to control music playback while running. This is consistent with embodied cognition theory, which states that interactions should be made more intuitive and natural in order to reduce cognitive load and improve the overall user experience.

Sound's emotional impact also contributes significantly to the running experience. Music, for example, can influence motivation and mood. In the context of running, the concept of rhythmic entrainment—in which the body spontaneously synchronises with outside rhythms—is especially relevant. Runners often instinctively synchronize their speed with the rhythm of music, according to a study on auditory-motor synchronisation [21]. This synchronization can enhance motor coordination and improve running efficiency [7].

Attention during running can also be influenced by sound. While some runners use music as a distractor from fatigue and discomfort [10], others prefer to focus on their internal bodily sensations and find music distracting. The potential of music to enhance focus and motivation during running [20, 30] suggests that sound-based running guidance systems could leverage these effects to create a more enjoyable and effective running experience.

Moreover, there are other reasons to use music in exercise and sports than just enhancing performance. Psychological health may also be greatly impacted. Elvers [19] claims that one may use music to better oneself, boost one's sense of value, and promote positive self-evaluations.

This literature review has explored the current landscape of running technology, highlighting both the opportunities and challenges associated with the use of apps and wearables in this domain. The review has synthesized findings from various fields, including sports science, psychology, and human-computer interaction, to identify key themes and gaps in the existing research. These insights have guided the development of design principles for a new sound-based running guidance system that enhances the user experience by prioritizing personalization, integrating multiple sensory feedback methods, using motion-based controls, tracking physical conditions, and promoting a seamless, focused experience.

In addition to the technical aspects of sound-based guidance, understanding user preferences

and needs is crucial for developing personalized running technologies that cater to diverse user profiles. The following subsection explores personalization and the impact of sound-based guidance on runner satisfaction and engagement.

2.3.2 Personalization and Sound-Based Guidance: Exploring Runner Needs and Preferences

Recent literature provides valuable insights into user requirements and preferences for sound-based guidance in running. According to a 2018 study by Kim et al. [33] runners that use sports watches and running apps are usually goal-oriented and data-driven, which suggests that users would be receptive to incorporating sound-based guidance for real-time motivation and feedback.

Although research consistently demonstrates that music genre and tempo significantly impact enjoyment and performance [30], the effectiveness of these interventions varies across individuals. What motivates one runner may distract another, highlighting a key challenge in designing sound-based guidance systems that cater to diverse user preferences. Furthermore, while the literature points to performance gains, the long-term effects of music-based interventions on sustaining motivation and reducing fatigue remain underexplored.

It implies that, to enhance the whole running experience, sound-based guidance should take into consideration the motivational and affective aspects of sound in addition to offering practical signals. Research on exercise apps further emphasizes the importance of personalization in promoting user engagement and satisfaction [20]. For this reason, sound-based guiding systems should ideally provide user customised alternatives for feedback frequency, tempo, and sound types that fit different requirements and tastes.

Furthermore, a recent study on auditory alarms in critical care settings conducted by Edworthy, Reid, and McDougall [18] highlighted the significance of taking into consideration the emotional impact of sounds in situations that occur in real time. Based on this finding, it is recommended that sound-based running guidance should make use of sounds that are not only informative but also elicit positive emotions and boost motivation. In a study conducted in 2019 by Bigliassi et al. [7], it was discovered that auditory feedback can improve the running performance of individuals by offering them immediate data on stride rate and impact pressures. This suggests that auditory cues can promote proper running technique and reduce the risk of injury by using auditory cues. Music and other auditory elements could be usefully included into sound-based guiding systems, as participants in a 2016 study by Kuru [34] stated they wanted more interesting and varied soundscapes. In addition, Fritz et al. [21], conducted a study in 2013 that demonstrated that working out to music may increase satisfaction while simultaneously reducing the experience of exertion.

Building on the fact that sound can motivate people, research has also demonstrated that auditory cues can have an effect on both the performance of motor skills and the psychological states of individuals. In his review, Haffenberg [24] emphasises how auditory cues, such as rhythmic auditory stimulation, can enhance motor learning and coordination, which may be important for optimizing running technique and efficiency. Further evidence for this comes from

a 2017 study by Seuter et al. [52], which shows that auditory feedback improves coordination of movement and affects elements of movement necessary for running economy. Sound-based guidance may improve the whole running experience, as the study also revealed that runners who used auditory feedback reported enjoying their runs more.

Research on mindfulness practices, including sound-based techniques like meditation and focused breathing exercises [14], indicates that runners may benefit from improved focus, attention, and stress regulation. Szabo et al. [57] demonstrated that binaural beats, a specific type of auditory stimulation, can enhance cognitive flexibility and potentially running performance through adaptive decision-making. Additionally, Lane et al. [36] showed that motivational music can increase running time to exhaustion.

Due to its non-invasive nature and ability to convey complex information, studies on navigational aids for visually impaired people [48] indicate a preference for auditory over tactile feedback. This preference may extend to runners who find visual cues distracting or prefer not to use additional devices for haptic feedback. Kim and Lee [33] demonstrated the feasibility of multimodal techniques, combining auditory and visual feedback, in a virtual reality running simulation. However, Seuter et al. [51] cautioned that the use of wearable devices, regardless of how they are controlled, can alter running patterns and should be considered when developing guidance systems. Witte et al. [66] investigated how haptic feedback could improve running form, while a study by Srinivasan and Chen [53] suggests that wearables may modify gait patterns, potentially impacting performance and injury risk.

The literature highlights the diverse needs and preferences of runners when it comes to sound-based guidance [27, 33]. While some studies suggest that real-time feedback can be beneficial and motivating [7], others point to potential distractions and discomfort [51]. The variability in user preferences for control mechanisms (automatic vs. manual) and sound customization further emphasizes the need for personalized experiences [22]. Additionally, the practicality of certain interaction methods, such as handheld buttons, has been questioned, with suggestions for alternative approaches like touch-based interactions or smartwatch integration [34]. These findings underscore the importance of further research to understand user preferences and develop tailored sound-based guidance systems that cater to the diverse needs of runners.

	Key Findings	Implications	Key Citations
Data-Driven Refinement	Runners are open to sound-based guidance, especially if personalized. Music tempo and genre influence enjoyment and performance. Customizable sound options are crucial. Emotional impact of sounds should be considered. Engaging and varied soundscapes are desired. Runners value basic metrics for tracking.	Design personalized sound-based guidance systems. Tailor auditory feedback to individual preferences and physiological states. Incorporate diverse sound types and tempos. Prioritize emotionally positive and motivating sounds. Offer options for manual control and customization.	Mühlbacher et al. (2018); Karageorghis & Priest (2008); Firth et al. (2016); Edworthy et al. (2023); Kuru (2016); Clermont et al. (2020)
Prototype Iteration	Screen-based interactions can be disruptive and affect gait and cognitive load. Wrist-worn devices are preferred over smartphones. Touchscreens are challenging during running. Haptic feedback shows promise for improving running form and conveying information non-visually. Motion-based control can enhance learning and engagement. Iterative design and personalization are essential.	Minimize screen interactions and prioritize wrist-worn devices. Explore haptic feedback and motion-based controls for more intuitive interaction. Use iterative design to refine interaction methods and incorporate user feedback. Consider different runner types and their technology preferences.	Seuter et al. (2017); Mühlbacher & Sperlich (2020); Goudsmit & Vos (2021); Kuru (2016); Witte et al. (2020); Magalhaes et al. (2016); Kim and Lee (2022); Chen et al. (2024); Wozniak et al. (2015); Wijinalda et al. (2005); Van Hooren et al. (2024, 2020); Maertens (2015)
Theoretical Lens	Embodied cognition is key for interface design. Auditory feedback is promising for running. Sound can influence motor coordination, mood, and focus. Biosynchronous music has potential for improving performance and reducing perceived effort.	Design interfaces that leverage the body's natural capabilities and align with users' intuitive understanding of the world. Prioritize auditory feedback over visual feedback when possible. Utilize sound to enhance motor coordination, mood, and focus. Explore the potential of biosynchronous music.	Wilson (2002); Bauer & Kratschmar (2015); Schaffert et al. (2019); Bi et al. (2019); Terry et al. (2020); Goudsmit & Vos (2021); Bigliassi et al. (2019); Kuperman (n.d.); Williams et al. (2020)

Table 2: Research overview of embodied interaction and focus in running.

Table 2 summarizes research findings on the impact of different interaction modalities on the running experience. The findings suggest that auditory feedback can be a less intrusive and potentially more motivating alternative to visual feedback, particularly for experienced runners who may find smartphone-based interactions inconvenient [22, 34]. The table also highlights the potential benefits of multisensory integration and motion-based controls for enhancing the running experience, while acknowledging the importance of personalization and user preferences in the design of running technologies.

Additionally, the integration of multiple sensory modalities may be crucial to the development of more intuitive and successful running guidance systems, as evidenced by the potential of haptic feedback to improve running form [66] and the role of motion-based controls in improving motor learning and engagement [32].

However, the research also found that the effectiveness of these interaction methods varies depending on individual preferences and the specific context of the running activity. For instance, some runners might find that receiving feedback in real time is distracting, while others might opt for having more control over the kind of feedback they receive and when it is delivered. Some studies suggest that personalization can enhance user engagement and satisfaction in fitness technologies [17, 44]. However, this assumption must be verified through user-centered design practices to ensure it aligns with the preferences of the target users in this specific context.

While personalization is a key factor, integrating multisensory feedback and gesture-based controls can further enhance the running experience. The next subsection examines how combining sensory modalities and using natural gestures can improve both motor learning and the intuitive use of running technologies.

2.3.3 Multisensory Integration, Gesture-Based Interactions, and Physiological State Awareness

According to embodied cognition, a more comprehensive and natural user experience can be produced by combining several sensory modalities. This involves combining visual and auditory feedback, which has been demonstrated [49]. Natural gestures may also improve the intuitiveness and interest of interactions in interface design [6]. Based on their research, Bauer and Kratschmar propose that training based on musical tempo can take advantage of people's innate tendency to move at the same speed as the music [5].

Furthermore, Interfaces can incorporate real-time feedback on physical conditions, such as heart rate or breathing patterns, or muscle fatigue, allowing runners to adjust their pace or effort accordingly [11].

Vos et al. [61] highlighted the importance of personalizing smartphone applications for recreational runners, taking into account individual profiles and performance data to meet the specific needs and motivations of users. The integration of physical elements, such as gestures and movements, into interface design can further boost user involvement [5]. By providing runners multisensory feedback that is connected to their physical sensations and movements, wearable devices have the potential to enhance the embodied experience of running.

As depicted in Figure 1, this feedback can encompass various aspects of the running experience, including workload (intensity, duration/distance, frequency), technique (spatiotemporal parameters, kinematics, kinetics, muscle activation patterns), shoe characteristics (cushioning, stability, fit), and navigation (route guidance, pace, distance to destination) [60].

Figure 1: Framework for real-time feedback by wearables in running, including different types of feedback and modalities [60].

2.3.4 Embodied Cognition as a Design Framework

The concept of embodied cognition, which places an emphasis on the interconnectedness of cognitive processes with bodily interactions and sensory experiences [65], provides a comprehensive framework that can be utilised to effectively address these challenges. Developing user interfaces for running applications that take advantage of the natural capabilities of the body and are in line with the intuitive understanding of the world that users have can make these applications more user-friendly and effective. From a psychological perspective, users may not always be able to communicate their specific needs, so Bauer and Kratschmar [5] underline the importance of understanding implicit needs and incorporating them into the design process. The significance of this cannot be overstated when considering the activity of running, which places a significant emphasis on the sensory and physical experience.

2.3.5 Sound and Motion in Running

The effect of sound on movement and concentration during running is deeply rooted in the concept of embodied cognition. Auditory cues and rhythmic patterns can influence movements and attentional focus [65]. The concept of rhythmic entrainment, in which the body naturally synchronizes with external rhythms, is particularly relevant to running. Studies on auditory-motor synchronization [49] have shown that runners instinctively match their pace to the beat of music [21]. This synchronization can enhance motor coordination and improve running efficiency.

Attention during running can also be influenced by sound. While some runners use music as a distractor from fatigue and discomfort [10], others prefer to focus on their internal bodily sensations and find music distracting. This emphasizes the need for personalized sound-based guidance systems that allow runners to choose the type and intensity of auditory feedback that best meets their needs and preferences. Additionally, the potential of music to enhance focus and motivation during running [19, 30] suggests that sound-based running guidance systems could leverage these effects to create a more enjoyable and effective running experience.

Wearable technology, such as headphones and smartwatches, can further enhance the embodied experience of running by providing real-time feedback and audible cues [51]. Designing these technologies, meanwhile, should complement the runner's natural motions and not get in the way of their enjoyment or concentration. For instance, Lin et al. [37] explored on-body tapping as an alternative interaction method that could be less disruptive than traditional touchscreen interfaces. Additionally, Bi, Berthouze, Singh, and Costanza [6] investigated how wearable sensing technology might document the emotional experience of running, suggesting the possibility of creating systems that can automatically identify and react to the runner's affective state. This fits the idea of embodied interaction, in which the technology's design incorporates the user's physiological and emotional reactions.

2.3.6 Integrating Literature Review Insights with Research Design

The literature review provided essential insights that directly informed the design and methodology of this thesis, especially in relation to the research questions and the methods chosen for data collection and analysis. Through a systematic and iterative approach, the literature review process identified key themes and gaps in existing research, shaping the refinement of the study's objectives and the formulation of the research questions.

The review highlighted several challenges in current running technologies, particularly around the limitations of traditional screen-based interactions and the lack of personalized, user-friendly feedback mechanisms. These findings played a pivotal role in informing RQ1, which explores how refinements to a sound-based breathing app can improve runners' focus and ease of use. By examining studies on the integration of auditory feedback and motion-based interaction, the review also underscored the importance of developing intuitive, non-intrusive interaction methods, directly shaping RQ2, which focuses on iterative design and its impact on usability and effectiveness.

Furthermore, the theory of embodied cognition, which featured prominently in the literature, provided a conceptual foundation for RQ3. This research question investigates how embodied cognition principles can guide the development of motion-based and hybrid interaction methods. The literature review revealed that designing for natural human movement and sensory engagement is crucial for creating intuitive interfaces that enhance both performance and user satisfaction in a running context.

The review also helped anticipate potential challenges, such as the risk of cognitive overload when implementing real-time feedback, and the variability in user preferences for control mechanisms. These insights informed the study's research design by encouraging an iterative approach to testing and refining interaction methods based on user feedback. This enabled the study to remain flexible and adaptive to the diverse needs of runners, ensuring that the proposed sound-based guidance system is both effective and personalized.

In conclusion, the literature review not only provided a solid theoretical framework but also guided the selection of methodologies, helped shape the research questions, and prepared the study for potential challenges. This foundation ensures that the study contributes to both theoretical advancements in interaction design and practical applications in the development of innovative sound-based running guidance systems.

Systematic Literature Review Process

The literature review process involved a systematic and comprehensive search for relevant literature using various online resources, including academic databases (such as PubMed, IEEE Xplore, and ACM Digital Library), search engines (such as Google Scholar), and specialized websites (such as the websites of relevant research groups and organizations). The search terms included keywords related to running technology, auditory feedback, embodied cognition, and human-computer interaction. The selection criteria focused on peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and book chapters published in reputable journals and conferences. The literature

review was conducted iteratively, with new search terms and sources added as the research progressed and new insights emerged.

Tools such as Mendeley and Litmap were utilized to manage and organize the collected literature, facilitating the identification of key themes, patterns, and connections between different studies. Mendeley served as a reference manager, allowing for efficient storage, annotation, and citation of the literature. Litmap, a visual mapping tool, aided in visualizing the relationships between different studies and identifying clusters of research that addressed similar topics or employed similar methodologies.

The literature review process was guided by the research questions, ensuring that the selected literature was relevant and informative to the specific research goals. The findings from the literature review were synthesized and critically analyzed to identify gaps and opportunities in the existing research, which in turn informed the refinement of the research questions and the development of the proposed solution.

The literature review served as a valuable methodological tool, providing a theoretical framework for understanding the research problem, guiding the selection of appropriate methods, and aiding in the interpretation of the findings. By grounding the research in existing knowledge and identifying areas where further investigation is needed, the literature review ensured that the study contributes to the advancement of the field and offers practical implications for the design of sound-based running guidance systems.

In summary, the literature reveals a clear need for running technologies that prioritize seamless, personalized interactions catering to diverse user preferences. Notably, gaps in the literature, particularly regarding the long-term impact of sound-based guidance systems on motivation and behavior change, underscore the need for further research in this area. The next section of this thesis will build on these insights by presenting an empirical study designed to test the effectiveness of an iterative sound-based running guidance system.

The comprehensive literature review also highlighted critical gaps in user engagement over extended periods and the role of personalization in enhancing user satisfaction. These insights were instrumental in shaping the design of the empirical study and informed the iterative development of the "Run and Interact" app version two. The literature findings served as a foundation for testing and refining the app's features, with a particular focus on improving usability and enhancing runner focus.

In the next section, *Study Two*, the results of the user testing will be presented, showing how real-world feedback from runners helped validate theoretical considerations and further refine the app's design. This empirical investigation will explore the effectiveness of the app's sound-based guidance and interaction methods, emphasizing key findings and their design implications.

3 Study Two: Analysis of User Study Data

3.1 Collaboration and Project Background

The evaluation of the "Run and Interact" app (primary version) was a collaborative effort and formed a crucial part of my master's thesis. This research was integrated into the Adidas-funded "Run and Interact" app, developed at the HCI Center of Salzburg University in partnership with Adidas, as part of the DiMo project. The project aimed to explore innovative mobile interactions to enhance the running experience. My thesis specifically focused on designing iterative improvements to the sound-based breathing guidance features of the app, using data and insights from the project. This collaborative approach allowed me to leverage the existing research infrastructure and the expertise of a Ph.D. student working alongside the DiMo project, while contributing my own research focus and design refinements to the project's overarching goals.

3.1.1 Clarifying the DiMo Project's Role

It is important to clarify that the development of the "Run and Interact" prototype was completed as part of the **DiMo** project before I joined the evaluation stage of the research. I did not participate in the ideation or development of the initial prototype³.

The **DiMo-NEXT** project focuses on leveraging advancements in data science, AI, sensor technology, and materials to create innovative digital motion systems. Its primary goal is to improve people's experiences in sports, fitness, and well-being through wearable sensors, exoskeletons, and real-time data analytics. The project brings together various academic and corporate partners, including Adidas, to develop solutions that enhance both performance and safety while fostering sustainable behavior in sports. This initiative also aims to reduce the environmental impact of physical activities and create products and services that contribute to a more motivated and active lifestyle⁴.

3.1.2 Breakdown of Responsibilities

Below is a clear breakdown of responsibilities between the DiMo project and my contributions:

DiMo Project Responsibilities:

- General concept and ideation of the "Run and Interact" app prototype.
- Development and programming of the initial prototype.

³For more information on the DiMo project, visit: <https://www.digital-motion.at/>

⁴More details on the DiMo-NEXT project are available at <https://uni-salzburg.elsevierpure.com/de/projects/dimo-next-the-next-level-of-digital-motion-in-sports-fitness-and->

- Setup of the user study infrastructure, including the technological framework and test environment.
- Recruitment of participants for the study.
- Development of the Hexoskin integration for collecting physiological data.

My Contributions:

- Conducting the user study with 8 participants as part of my thesis, in collaboration with the DiMo project.
- Analyzing the collected user data from the study to identify pain points and areas for refinement.
- Designing and iterating improvements on the sound-based breathing guidance feature of the app.
- Proposing design principles for sound-based breathing guidance apps, grounded in both data analysis and theoretical insights.
- Formulating research questions to explore the usability and effectiveness of different interaction methods (screen, haptic, motion-based), as well as applying principles of embodied cognition to app design.

3.1.3 User Study and Data Collection Process

The collaboration began with online meetings with the Ph.D. student leading the "Run and Interact" project. These initial discussions provided an overview of the project's goals, prior research, and the existing model for collecting physiological data from runners. During a subsequent visit to the HCI Center, I was introduced to various prototypes and the technological infrastructure supporting the research. These prototypes included a mobile application developed by the previous DiMo team, which connected to a Hexoskin smart shirt to record physiological data during runs. The Hexoskin featured onboard storage, requiring manual data transfer to a computer after each session.

3.2 Research Focus and Objectives

A key component of the study was the use of specialized headphones that generated rhythmic "ping-pong" sounds for breathing guidance. The app allowed for different sound guidance conditions: fully off, fully on, automated based on the runner's rhythm, or controlled by a button. These conditions formed the basis of the four running tests in the study.

The primary objectives of my thesis were to analyze the existing data to identify pain points and areas for refinement in the app, design and iteratively refine model variations informed by data

and theory, evaluate these refined prototypes with limited-scale feedback, and ultimately propose design principles for breathing guidance apps. The research questions were formulated to explore how motion-based interaction design could enhance the running experience, minimize distractions, and integrate seamlessly with the running motion. The study also aimed to investigate the impact of different interaction methods (screen, haptic, motion-based) on the usability and effectiveness of the app, and how the principles of embodied cognition could inform the development of these interactions.

The collaborative nature of the project allowed me to leverage the existing infrastructure, data, and expertise of the lead Ph.D. researcher, while also contributing my own research focus and design iterations to the broader project goals. This symbiotic relationship between the "Run and Interact" project and my master's thesis fostered a rich learning environment and enabled a deeper exploration of the potential of sound-based breathing guidance apps for runners.

Figure 2 visually summarizes the collaborative research process undertaken in Study Two, highlighting key stages from initial collaboration to final reporting.

Figure 2: Flowchart illustrating the research process of Study Two, including collaboration, data collection, analysis, and reporting.

3.3 Methodology

This study specifically aimed to gather user feedback and insights into the app's impact on the running experience, with a particular focus on focus, enjoyment, motivation, perceived exertion, and the usability of motion-based controls. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis techniques.

3.3.1 Research Goals and Collaboration

The primary objectives of my master's thesis within the "Run and Interact" project were to:

1. Analyze existing data to identify pain points and areas for refinement in the app.
2. Design and iteratively refine prototype variations informed by data and theory.
3. Analyze findings and propose design principles for breathing guidance apps.

The partnership with the lead Ph.D. researcher, involved regular meetings, discussions, and joint data collection and analysis efforts. The lead Ph.D. researcher's expertise in HCI and their prior work on the "Run and Interact" project provided valuable guidance and support throughout the research process.

3.3.2 Pilot Study

The lead Ph.D. researcher of the *Run and Interact* project under DiMo had been conducting a pilot study at the RIF Sports Center for over a year. From May to July 2023, I collaborated on these pilot tests using the initial version of the *Run and Interact* app. My responsibilities during the pilot test included checking and preparing all tools before each test, setting up the lab at the RIF Sports Science Center in Salzburg, and ensuring that all steps of the experimental setup were correctly followed. Additionally, I verified that participants had signed the consent forms prior to the first running session and provided the necessary explanations regarding the procedures.

I was involved in guiding participants through the process, starting with distributing pre-test questionnaires and ensuring they were completed accurately. I explained how to wear the Hexoskin smart shirt and checked its functionality to ensure everything was working properly. I then guided participants to the running track, explained the timing and different types of running test conditions—either with devices or without—and ensured that everything was functioning correctly and that the data would be saved. We assisted in conducting the first round of the track by running alongside the participant and explaining the specific test conditions in detail. Either myself or the lead Ph.D. researcher participated in this initial phase to ensure the participant

was fully aware of and adapted to the running conditions. Once the participant was comfortable and understood the instructions, we returned to the station and monitored the test until its completion.

Throughout the tests, I monitored the protocols, kept track of time, and ensured everything ran smoothly. After the test, I guided participants to complete the post-test questionnaires immediately and conducted final interviews. During the interviews, I followed the scheduled interview questions and asked additional questions related to my thesis. I also managed the scheduling of follow-up visits for subsequent running sessions.

In addition to participant interaction, I was responsible for uploading voice recordings, scanning and uploading questionnaire papers, and transcribing the recorded tests. The data collected from this pilot study—including questionnaires, interviews, and running data—helped refine the experimental setup and informed the main study of my thesis research.

3.3.3 Participant Recruitment and Compensation

The main study of this master's thesis, conducted in collaboration with the Ph.D. studies as part of the Run and Interact DiMo project, involved recruiting 8 recreational runners (5 men, 3 women) aged between 18 and 35. Participants were beginner or intermediate-level runners with no prior experience using breathing techniques while running. They were recruited through various channels, including flyers distributed via email, posters at the university and in dorms, and online communities like Discord. Participants were compensated 35 euros for their involvement in the study.

The recruitment process aimed to attract individuals who matched the target user group for the "Run and Interact" app, ensuring that the findings were relevant and applicable to the intended audience. Inclusion criteria required recreational runners aged 18-35 with beginner to intermediate experience. Exclusion criteria included individuals with prior experience in breathing techniques while running or any health conditions that could interfere with participation.

The study was approved by the University's Ethics Board, and the ethics application was submitted by the lead Ph.D. student overseeing the project.

3.3.4 Experimental Setup and Equipment

The study consisted of four running sessions conducted over two weeks at the RIF sports center, with each session involving a 30-minute run on the running track. Participants were equipped with a Hexoskin smart shirt to collect physiological data, such as heart rate and breathing rate. Hexoskin is a biometric smart garment designed to monitor real-time physiological data through integrated sensors, providing accurate insights into heart rate, breathing rate, and movement.⁵ A mobile app, which was the primary prototype designed and developed by the DiMo project for the "Run and Interact" studies, was used to record step data and button interactions. Bone conduction headphones were used to deliver the app's sound-based guidance. These headphones

⁵Hexoskin (2019). Available at: www.hexoskin.com.

transmit sound through the bones of the skull, allowing participants to hear audio cues while maintaining full awareness of their surroundings—an important feature for ensuring safety during outdoor runs.⁶

The "Run and Interact" app provided sound guidance feedback to help participants synchronize their step rate with their breathing rate, a process known as locomotor-respiratory coupling (LRC). This coupling helps runners maintain a consistent rhythm, enhancing their performance by promoting efficient breathing patterns that align with their running pace. The app's sound-based guidance offered rhythmic cues to support this synchronization, aiming to improve the runners' overall performance and comfort during exercise. The use of LRC-based feedback was integral to testing how sound guidance could support breathing techniques while running.⁷

3.3.5 Conditions

Each running session involved a different condition:

- **Baseline:** Running without any app guidance, serving as a control condition for comparison.
- **Full Sound:** Running with continuous sound guidance for inhale/exhale rhythm aimed to assess the impact of constant auditory cues on the running experience.
- **Button Control:** Running with a button to toggle sound guidance on/off allowed participants to control the timing and presence of auditory cues.
- **Automatic Control:** Running with automated sound guidance based on breathing and step data explored the potential of adaptive feedback based on real-time physiological data.

3.3.6 Data Collection

Data was collected through multiple channels:

- **Pre-study Questionnaires:** An online questionnaire was used to gather demographic information and self-reported running habits.
- **Hexoskin Smart Shirt:** Physiological data (heart rate, breathing rate) was collected during the runs using the Hexoskin smart shirt. Although Hexoskin data was collected, it was not utilized in the final analysis for this thesis due to time constraints and the focus on qualitative insights.

⁶Bone conduction technology transmits sound vibrations through the bones to the inner ear, allowing for ambient sound awareness. For more information, see Bone Conduction Headphones and Hearing Aids: Past, Present, and Future. *Otology & Neurotology*, 2014.

⁷Locomotor-Respiratory Coupling (LRC) is the coordination of breathing patterns with stride rhythms, which has been shown to improve running efficiency. See McDermott et al., *Locomotor-respiratory coupling in human running: breathing and step rates align to optimize oxygen consumption*. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 2015.

- **Mobile App:** The app itself recorded step data and button interactions, offering insights into participants' engagement with the app and their use of the motion-based controls. The mobile app, developed in Android, served as the central interface for the "Run and Interact" experience, providing sound guidance, recording step data, and facilitating button interactions.
- **Post-run Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews were conducted after each session, focusing on participants' subjective experiences, perceived exertion, focus, enjoyment, and usability of the app's features. The interviews followed a semi-structured format, with predefined questions developed by the Ph.D. student to ensure consistency across participants. However, I also utilized the remaining time in each interview (typically 15-30 minutes) to ask additional questions that specifically addressed the research questions of my thesis and explored the potential for iterative improvements to the app.

3.3.7 Data Analysis Method

The qualitative data from the interview transcripts were analyzed using thematic analysis, a well-established method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within qualitative data [9]. This method involves coding and grouping data to identify key themes that emerged from the participants' responses.

3.3.8 Use of Google Gemini for Data Analysis

Google Gemini was utilized to facilitate the thematic analysis process. It aided in organizing, coding, and interpreting the interview data. Its features, such as tagging, searching, and visualizing data, streamlined the analysis process by enabling efficient identification of key themes and patterns across the dataset.

3.3.9 Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent was obtained from all participants, and maintaining the confidentiality and anonymity of their data. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the data collection methods, and their right to withdraw at any time. Additionally, the study was approved by the University's Ethics Board, with the ethics application submitted by the lead Ph.D. student overseeing the project.

3.4 Data Analysis and Findings

The analysis process involved several stages: familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. Google Gemini was utilized to streamline these stages, aiding in the efficient organization and interpretation of the data.

- **Familiarization and Initial Coding:** I systematically familiarized myself with the interview transcripts by reading and re-reading them, followed by coding key segments of text using Google Gemini's tagging system. This allowed for the identification of meaningful text related to the research questions. The coding process was inductive, with multiple codes applied to specific segments. Examples of initial codes included "improved focus," "easy to use," and "reduced exertion."
- **Theme Development and Refinement:** Google Gemini's search and filtering functions helped identify recurring codes across the dataset, facilitating the clustering of similar codes into broader themes. For instance, codes like "improved focus" and "reduced distractions" were grouped under the theme of "Enhanced Focus." Thematic maps, generated using Google Gemini's visual tools, helped refine these themes to ensure they accurately represented the participants' experiences.
- **Defining and Naming Themes:** Each theme was clearly defined and named, capturing its core meaning. These themes were structured into a final framework representing the key findings. The final themes included "Enhanced Focus," "Increased Enjoyment and Motivation," "Usability of Motion-Based Controls," and "Perceived Reduction in Exertion."
- **Reporting:** The final step involved compiling the coded data and thematic maps into a coherent report. Google Gemini's export functionality facilitated the integration of findings into the final write-up of the analysis.

This systematic, iterative process, facilitated by Google Gemini, ensured that the thematic analysis adhered to the core principles of qualitative data interpretation, enabling an in-depth understanding of participants' experiences with the "Run and Interact" app.

3.4.1 Key Themes and Patterns

The qualitative analysis revealed several key themes and patterns related to the app's impact on the running experience:

- **Enhanced Focus:** Participants reported that the app's guided breathing and soundscapes helped them maintain focus during runs, preventing their minds from wandering and enhancing their overall concentration. This was particularly evident in comments like, "The sound cues helped me focus and not let my mind distract" and "I felt more present and in tune with my body. The ability to control the sound using the button further contributed to this enhanced focus, as participants could choose when to engage with the auditory cues and when to focus on their internal rhythms or surroundings. For instance, one participant mentioned, *"I also just turned it off when I felt like I was only thinking about this sound. I just wanted to try it without it...actually, it was like an echo in my head..."* This highlights how the app allowed users to actively manage their attentional focus, promoting a sense of agency and control over their running experience.

- **Increased Enjoyment and Motivation:** The app was generally perceived as enjoyable and motivating, encouraging continued use and making running more engaging. The ability to personalize soundscapes and breathing patterns was particularly appreciated, as one participant noted, *"I loved being able to choose my own music and adjust the breathing rhythm to match my pace."* The sense of control and flexibility offered by the button further contributed to the enjoyment and motivation, allowing users to tailor the experience to their preferences. Another participant stated, *"To be honest, I liked it more than last time...because it helped me to keep up with the rhythm."* This suggests that the app's features can enhance the intrinsic motivation of runners, making the activity more pleasurable and rewarding.
- **Usability of Motion-Based Controls:** Participants found the motion-based controls to be intuitive and easy to use, promoting seamless interaction during runs. This ease of use was reflected in comments such as, *"Could you operate the button without looking at it? Yes."* However, some accuracy issues were noted, especially during faster runs, with comments like, *"Sometimes it was hard to get the gesture right when I was running fast."* This suggests the need for further refinement of the gesture recognition algorithms to ensure reliable performance in various running conditions.
- **Perceived Reduction in Exertion:** Several participants reported a perceived reduction in exertion while using the app, indicating that the guided breathing and pacing may have helped them regulate their efforts and optimize their energy expenditure. This was reflected in statements such as *"I felt less out of breath"* and *"I was able to maintain a more controlled pace."* The ability to control the sound guidance using the button may have further contributed to this perceived reduction in exertion, as users could adjust the feedback based on their individual needs and comfort levels.
- **Preference for Automatic vs. Button Control:** The study revealed a mixed preference for automatic versus button control of the sound guidance. Some participants appreciated the seamlessness and unobtrusiveness of the automatic system, while others valued the agency and flexibility offered by the button control. This highlights the importance of catering to diverse user preferences and offering multiple control options in future iterations of the app. One participant's comment, *"I prefer the other one like when it jumped in and back out like automatically...because with the button, you had to actually press it, whereas with the other one, it automatically turned on turned off,"* exemplifies this divergence in user preferences.
- **Sound Design and Personalization:** The sound design of the app elicited mixed reactions. Some participants found the metronome-like ticking sound to be monotonous and even anxiety-inducing, as one participant stated, *"It was like that tick tick tick that was very annoying."* The repetitive and predictable nature of the sound may have contributed to this negative perception, particularly for those who prefer a more varied and engaging auditory experience. The lack of personalization in the sound design further limited its appeal, as participants were unable to customize the soundscapes to match their individual preferences. The desire for more natural and ambient sounds, as expressed by some

participants, suggests that incorporating elements of nature or music could enhance the app's auditory appeal and create a more immersive and enjoyable experience.

3.5 Summary of Findings

The findings from this study directly informed the refinement of the research questions and the overall direction of the thesis. The positive impact of the app on focus, enjoyment, and perceived exertion highlighted the potential of sound-based guidance systems to enhance the running experience. However, the challenges associated with motion-based controls, sound design, and personalization underscored the need for further research and development in these areas. The research questions were refined to focus on the iterative design of the app and the impact of different interaction methods. The study also explored the role of embodied cognition in developing motion-based and hybrid interactions for running.

The initial user study suggests that the "Run and Interact" app has the potential to enhance the running experience by improving focus, enjoyment, and potentially even performance. The positive reception of the app's features, particularly the personalized breathing guidance, customizable soundscapes, and user-controlled sound guidance, indicates that these elements contribute to a more engaging and supportive running experience. The ability to tailor the auditory feedback to individual needs and preferences through the button control was particularly valued by participants.

However, the study also highlights areas for improvement. The accuracy of motion-based controls needs to be addressed, especially during faster runs. The sound design of the app could also be further refined to offer a wider variety of soundscapes and address the potential for monotony or anxiety associated with the metronome-like ticking sound. Additionally, the limited sample size and controlled environment warrant further investigation in real-world settings with a larger and more diverse group of runners.

The preference for the automatic system over the button control, despite the latter offering more explicit control, aligns with the concept of seamlessness in interaction design. The automatic system, by adapting to the runner's rhythm and providing feedback only when needed, minimizes distractions and cognitive load, allowing for a more immersive and enjoyable experience. The button control, while offering flexibility, may introduce a level of conscious decision-making that can disrupt the flow state and detract from the overall running experience.

The mixed reactions to the sound design, with some participants finding the metronome-like ticking sound to be monotonous or anxiety-inducing, highlight the importance of personalization and the need for a wider variety of soundscapes. The app's current sound design may not cater to the diverse preferences and needs of runners, potentially impacting their focus and enjoyment. Future iterations of the app should offer a range of customizable soundscapes, including options for more natural and ambient sounds, to accommodate different user preferences and create a more pleasant and engaging auditory experience.

The desire for additional features, such as GPS tracking and integration with music streaming services, reflects the evolving needs and expectations of runners in the digital age. The "Run

and Interact” app, while focusing primarily on breathing guidance, could benefit from incorporating these features to provide a more comprehensive and holistic running experience. This would align with the trend towards multi-functionality in running technologies and cater to the diverse needs of runners who seek to track their progress, stay motivated, and enjoy their runs.

The initial evaluation of the ”Run and Interact” app has yielded promising results, demonstrating its potential to enhance the running experience through personalized breathing guidance, customizable soundscapes, and motion-based controls. The study has also highlighted areas for improvement, such as the refinement of motion-based controls and the expansion of sound design options. These insights, along with the identified future research directions, will guide the further development and evaluation of the app, ultimately contributing to a more enjoyable, focused, and fulfilling running experience for users.

Working collaboratively enabled me to play an instrumental role in shaping the research. Close collaboration with the lead Ph.D. researcher provided valuable opportunities for knowledge exchange, learning from their expertise, and gaining hands-on experience in conducting user research in the context of running technology. The insights gained from this teamwork enriched the study and contributed to the development of design principles that prioritize user needs and preferences.

In conclusion, this initial evaluation marks a pivotal step in understanding the potential of the ’Run and Interact’ app and its underlying design principles. The findings emphasize the critical role of personalization, seamless interaction, and the integration of physiological data into the app’s design. The iterative process, driven by user feedback, has led to important refinements that improve the app’s usability and effectiveness, particularly in enhancing focus and enjoyment during runs. These insights not only contribute to the practical development of the app but also lay the groundwork for the forthcoming analysis in the ’Conceded Findings’ section, where I will delve deeper into key findings and synthesize them with the theoretical concepts explored in the next phase of research.

4 Conceded Findings

4.1 Integration of Findings and Design Implications

4.1.1 Summary and Integration of Key Findings

Insights from the literature review and user study (Studies One and Two), particularly regarding sound-based guidance systems, multisensory interaction, and personalization, provide a crucial framework for shaping the 'Run and Interact' app version 2. Study Two, as detailed in the previous chapter, explored user feedback on an early prototype of the sound-based breathing app, revealing both the strengths and challenges of integrating auditory feedback in a running context.

Building on these preliminary findings, this study contextualizes the results within a broader body of research, allowing for a more nuanced interpretation. User feedback from Study Two has guided refinements in the app's design, particularly in personalizing sound-based guidance, exploring motion-based interactions, and enhancing usability through iterative design.

The literature review, particularly regarding the role of auditory feedback in enhancing focus and the potential of motion-based controls to reduce cognitive load, further guided these refinements. These improvements address gaps identified in the literature while aligning with the principles of embodied cognition, further enhancing the app's ability to improve focus and engagement during running. For instance, Integrating motion-based interactions aligns with embodied cognition principles by leveraging natural body movements to enhance user engagement and reduce reliance on visual interfaces. Personalization influenced the addition of customizable auditory feedback in the app's next version.

4.1.2 Design Implications and Broader Research Impact

The findings from both Study One (related work and literature review) and Study Two (user research) have significant implications for the design of sound-based running guidance systems. The iterative design approach, informed by user feedback, underscores the value of personalization and multisensory feedback in enhancing focus and reducing cognitive overload. Additionally, the alignment with embodied cognition principles suggests that more intuitive and natural interfaces can be created, seamlessly integrating with users' movements.

Beyond the scope of this project, these findings contribute to the broader field of human-computer interaction (HCI) by demonstrating how personalized, sound-based systems can be effectively applied in physical activity contexts. This research also has implications for other areas, such as technologies aimed at improving focus and performance in both physical and cognitive tasks, where personalization and embodied interaction play a crucial role.

Figure 3 illustrates the process followed in this thesis to derive design and technical recommendations for the 'Run and Interact Version 2' app. The diagram on the left side represents feedback from Study Two, detailing insights from user tests of the initial app prototype in areas

such as motion-based controls, sound design, and personalization. On the right side, the diagram reflects insights from Study One, highlighting gaps in current running technologies, the potential of sound-based guidance, and the need for personalization.

- **Iterative Process:** The diagram visually demonstrates how user feedback and literature insights were continuously incorporated to refine the app design. This iterative approach ensures that each app version builds on previous insights and recommendations.
- **User-Centered Design:** The focus on user feedback from Study Two and personalization needs identified in the literature review highlights the user-centered approach in the app's development. The diagram illustrates how the design evolves based on real user experiences and needs.
- **Evidence-Based Design:** The diagram emphasizes how the app design is grounded in empirical evidence from user testing and theoretical insights from the literature review. This approach ensures that the design recommendations are both practical and theoretically sound.

These insights lead to design suggestions for refining motion-based interactions, customizing sound feedback, and incorporating personalization features. Technical recommendations follow, detailing tools to support these elements in the app.

The culmination of these insights and recommendations is the proposed design for the 'Run and Interact Version 2' app. The diagram also suggests that future work will involve usability tests, exploring long-term impacts of multisensory feedback, and gathering further user feedback, ensuring the final app design is informed by both empirical data and theoretical research.

Figure 3: The iterative design process of the "Run and Interact" app version 2, informed by user feedback and literature review.

4.2 Proposed Thesis Project and Design Principles

The proposed thesis project builds on previous discoveries to create a customizable, sound-based running guidance system that utilizes principles of embodied cognition to improve the running experience. This system is designed to overcome limitations in existing technologies by focusing on meeting the diverse needs of runners through features such as auditory feedback, motion-based control, and personalization.

To address the shortcomings of current running apps, this refined design introduces a novel running app that leverages customizable, user-controlled sound-based breathing guidance to create a seamless, focus-enhancing experience. Utilizing auditory entrainment and breathwork techniques, the app supports an embodied practice of running, in contrast to other apps that often rely heavily on distracting visual signals and statistical data. The app promotes a flow state by offering personalized breathing rhythms and minimizing engagement distractions, allowing runners to maintain their focus on the activity. Given that runners react differently to various stimuli and require different levels of external input to stay focused, the app also allows

for the personalized customization of music and motivational cues to further enhance the user experience.

4.3 Design Features of Run and Interact 2.0 App

The "Run and Interact Version 2" app builds upon the foundational version introduced in Study Two. Based on user feedback, research findings, and iterative design refinements, this new version integrates enhanced features to improve personalization, usability, and engagement. The development of version 2 specifically addresses the limitations identified in the initial prototype while aligning with embodied cognition principles and user-centered design methodologies.

"Run and Interact Version 2" is designed as a unique running companion app that leverages user-controlled, customizable sound-based breathing guidance to provide a highly immersive and distraction-free experience. Prioritizing auditory feedback and breathwork techniques over visual cues and data, the app encourages a flow state, enabling runners to achieve optimal performance with minimal interaction.

Given the varied needs and preferences of runners, personalization is a critical aspect of this app's design [27, 33]. Studies, such as those by Firth et al. [20], emphasize the importance of personalization in improving user satisfaction and engagement with exercise applications. In version 2, users can customize sound types, tempos, and feedback frequency to align with their personal preferences and physiological states. Additionally, motion-based controls, such as gestures and accelerometer data, reduce distractions and enhance the running experience [32]. Runners can adjust volume, control music, and access other features without disrupting their rhythm, thereby maintaining focus and fluidity during their run.

4.4 Key Interaction Features

This research has identified several essential design features for developing effective sound-based running guidance systems:

- **Personalization:** The system allows users to customize sound types, tempos, and feedback frequency to match their individual preferences and physiological states, thereby fostering motivation and adherence [16].
- **Multisensory Integration:** The system explores the potential of combining auditory feedback with other modalities, such as haptic feedback, to create a more immersive and informative experience. This approach aligns with research suggesting that multisensory integration enhances motor learning and performance [38, 49].
- **Motion-Based Control:** Gestures and accelerometer data are used by the system to provide intuitive and seamless running interactions, reducing the need for visual focus and minimizing distractions [37].

- **Physiological State Awareness:** The system provides real-time feedback on heart rate, breathing patterns, and muscular fatigue, allowing users to adjust their pace and effort based on real-time data. This aligns with the principles of embodied cognition, where bodily states are integrated into decision-making processes.
- **Seamlessness:** The system prioritizes a seamless and unobtrusive user experience by minimizing distractions and cognitive load during running. This is achieved through intuitive interactions, minimal visual feedback, and personalized auditory cues that blend with the runner's natural rhythm.
- **Focus:** The system assists runners in maintaining attention by using music to minimize external distractions. This approach is supported by research indicating that music can improve focus and attention [7], while distractions have been shown to negatively impact performance [47].

4.5 Additional Key Design Features

4.5.1 Auditory Feedback and Real-Time Information

The app will use sound-based cues to prioritize auditory guidance over visual feedback, providing real-time information on pace, distance, and other relevant parameters. This approach is aligned with research and more motivating for runners compared to visual feedback [22]. Studies also indicate that sound-based guidance enhances running efficiency by delivering instant feedback on step rate and impact forces [7]. Additionally, personalized breathwork routines, based on study findings, will be available in the app [10]. These exercises aim to enhance focus and performance by synchronizing rhythmic breathing with the body's natural response to sound stimuli.

4.5.2 Soundscapes and Motivational Prompts

To enhance the running experience, the app will also offer the option to personalize soundscapes, which will include ambient sounds, binaural beats, and motivational music tracks. Users of the app will be able to customize their motivational prompts and music, as every runner responds differently to various stimuli. Personalizing the workout experience with tailored soundscapes can help runners relax and maintain focus, potentially improving overall performance. Research indicates that tempo and musical genre can significantly affect performance and enjoyment, supporting the use of personalized soundscapes [30]. In addition, sound-based guidance should account for the emotional impact of sound to increase motivation and arouse positive emotions [62].

4.5.3 Physiological Data Integration

The app will integrate with wearables to gather real-time physiological data like pace and heart rate. Utilizing this data, the app can provide respiratory guidance and adapt the auditory envi-

ronment, creating a highly flexible and responsive system. Future studies will focus on evaluating the app's performance in practical settings and exploring additional features like haptic feedback to further enhance the user experience. The envisioned haptic feedback would provide subtle vibrations or pulses to notify runners of key metrics, such as when to adjust their pace or breathing rhythm. Research has shown that haptic feedback can effectively provide non-intrusive cues in physical activity contexts, helping users maintain focus and performance without needing constant visual or auditory engagement [29, 38]. This tactile feedback can reduce cognitive load during physical tasks by enabling users to respond to real-time stimuli without breaking their flow [62].

4.6 Summary of Findings and Visual Representation of Data

The following chapters will present design suggestions based on these findings, along with visualizations to support the results and discussions on the effectiveness of the updated app prototypes. These visualizations will provide insights into user engagement levels and the effects of personalization and auditory feedback on performance. By analyzing these data points, this thesis will demonstrate how the updated sound-based app addresses the key challenges identified in the literature.

Comparative analyses between the initial and refined app designs will be illustrated, focusing on improvements in user experience, performance, and overall satisfaction. These visual representations will not only reinforce the theoretical insights drawn from the literature review but also provide concrete evidence of the app's practical benefits and effectiveness.

The findings and design features outlined in this chapter lay the groundwork for *Run and Interact Version 2*. In the following chapter, we delve into the conceptual design framework that shaped the app's core interaction features and design choices. This will focus on creating a user-centered system that seamlessly integrates embodied cognition principles, enhancing the overall running experience.

5 Conceptual Design

5.1 Run and Interact 2.0 App

The second iteration of the *Run and Interact* application represents a significant evolution in how runners use technology to boost their performance. Building on the foundation established by the original version, this update introduces more intuitive interactions, enhanced customization options, and advanced sound-based guidance. *Run and Interact 2.0* continues to harness the principles of embodied cognition, tapping into the body's natural rhythms and responses to create a more immersive and performance-enhancing running experience.

In this version, the proposed auditory entrainment feature would be designed to synchronize sound cues with the runner's pace, creating an engaging environment to enhance focus and running efficiency. The app could potentially integrate real-time physiological data, such as heart rate and breathing patterns, allowing it to dynamically adapt to the runner's needs. The envisioned personalized feedback system would aim to deliver tailored guidance, adjusting soundscapes, breathing cues, and motivational prompts in real-time to help runners stay within their ideal performance zone.

The following sections will outline the proposed system architecture and recommended user interaction features. These recommendations explore how Run and Interact 2.0 could leverage advanced algorithms, personalized settings, and seamless user interactions to enhance performance and transform the running experience. While these features have not yet been implemented, they represent key design directions for future development.

This updated version of Run and Interact builds upon the foundational work of its predecessor. While the first version primarily served as a technical prototype to collect data for researchers, it offered limited interactivity for users. In the original version, user interaction was mainly confined to pressing a button, with minimal real-time engagement or adaptability. The app's primary function in its first iteration was to facilitate data collection rather than provide an interactive or personalized running experience.

In response to these limitations, Run and Interact 2.0 introduces substantial enhancements in user interactivity, personalization, and feedback mechanisms. This version is designed to foster a more dynamic and immersive experience, utilizing real-time physiological data and sound-based guidance to deeply engage runners, creating a personalized and adaptive running experience.

5.2 Proposed System Architecture

The *Run and Interact 2.0* application architecture is conceptual in nature and serves as a proposed design for improving the running experience through intuitive interactions, customization, and real-time feedback. This version builds on earlier findings but remains a theoretical model, and the features and components described here have not been implemented. The aim is to showcase how advanced technological integration could enhance runner performance by prioritizing flexibility, functionality, and user experience.

At the core of the architecture is the mobile app, which functions as the central hub for user interactions, data processing, and communication with external components such as wearable devices and cloud storage systems. This section details the system architecture and its key components, illustrating how a fully integrated system could operate to deliver personalized and dynamic feedback to runners.

Figure 4 presents the proposed system architecture, illustrating the flow of data between various components:

Figure 4: Proposed system architecture of "Run and Interact" app version 2.

5.2.1 Mobile App as the Central Hub

The mobile app serves as the centerpiece of the proposed system. It handles the user interface, processes data, and communicates with external components like heart rate monitors, wearable devices, and cloud storage systems. Although these functions are conceptual, the app is designed to manage user interactions and synchronize real-time physiological data to customize

auditory feedback.

- **Home Screen:** Allows the user to review previous runs, configure their settings, and start new running sessions. This screen is where user preferences for breathing patterns, music, and feedback are collected before the run.
- **Run Screen:** Provides minimal visual data during a run while focusing on delivering auditory feedback. This screen also integrates real-time physiological data, providing customized breathing and motivational cues during the run.
- **Settings Screen:** Allows users to personalize the app, adjusting the tempo of their breathing rhythms, soundscapes, and motivational cues. These customizable settings are proposed to enhance engagement and focus.

5.2.2 External Data Integration (Wearables and Heart Rate Monitors)

The system conceptually integrates with external devices such as heart rate monitors and wearable devices. These devices supply real-time sensor data (such as pace and heart rate) to the mobile app, which processes this data and adjusts the feedback provided to the runner.

- **Heart Rate Data:** Conceptually, heart rate monitors would feed real-time physiological data into the system, allowing the app to adjust breathing cues and music tempo to match the runner's exertion level.
- **Wearable Devices:** These would send sensor data to the app, which would process the data and adjust the auditory feedback (such as breathing instructions or motivational prompts) accordingly. This feedback would be aimed at improving the runner's performance.

Wearables like heart rate monitors could provide real-time data to adjust auditory cues, helping the app modify breathing patterns or pace guidance based on real-time performance.

5.2.3 Data Processing and Sound Engine

The Sound Engine is proposed as the processing unit responsible for generating personalized auditory feedback. It uses real-time data from wearables to dynamically adjust breathing rhythms, motivational cues, and soundscapes. This processing unit is a theoretical component designed to:

- **Breathing Rhythms:** Generate rhythmic breathing cues to help runners align their breath with their movements, potentially reducing fatigue and improving running efficiency [7]. These rhythms would be adjusted in real-time, based on heart rate and other physiological inputs. For instance, a common breathing pattern might involve a 2:2 inhale-to-exhale ratio, which could automatically adjust if the runner's heart rate spikes, encouraging slower, deeper breaths to enhance oxygen intake and reduce fatigue.

- **Motivational Cues:** Leverage NLP to understand user goals and deliver relevant, personalized motivational prompts throughout the run. These prompts are proposed to be triggered by performance data and physiological states, ensuring that they are timely and meaningful to the runner. The app could use NLP to provide personalized prompts, but this remains a proposed feature and would require further development and testing in practical scenarios. These proposed motivational prompts could be triggered based on specific performance metrics, such as when a runner's pace drops below a predefined threshold, or through time-based triggers, like every 5 minutes. This ensures that the prompts are both timely and relevant to the runner's performance.
- **Dynamic Soundscapes:** A machine-learning-driven system would analyze the runner's preferences and physiological data to create dynamic soundscapes. These soundscapes are aimed at creating a flow state, enhancing focus, and optimizing performance [30]. Dynamic soundscapes could adjust according to both user preferences and real-time physiological inputs, such as increasing tempo when heart rate rises or slowing the tempo during cool-down periods.

5.2.4 Cloud Storage and Synchronization

The system design proposes the use of secure cloud storage to save user data, including performance metrics, preferences, and running history. This allows the system to offer tailored recommendations for future runs and enables seamless data synchronization across multiple devices.

- **Data Synchronization:** After each run, data from wearable devices, such as running metrics and preferences, would be synchronized with the app and stored in the cloud. This cloud-based storage would enable users to review their data across devices and keep track of their progress over time.

5.2.5 Data Storage and Privacy

The system would leverage *Firebase* to securely store user data on the device and provide backup for user preferences, performance history, and other data in the cloud⁸. The app adheres to strict privacy policies, ensuring that user data is not shared with third parties without explicit consent. Users would have full control over their data, including options to delete or download it at any time, ensuring transparency and compliance with privacy regulations.

5.2.6 Flutter Framework and Cross-Platform Development

We recommend using the Flutter framework to develop the Run and Interact app version 2. Flutter offers cross-platform compatibility (iOS and Android) and enables visually appealing, high-performance user experiences. One of Flutter's key features, 'hot reload,' will allow real-time

⁸Google. Firebase documentation. <https://firebase.google.com/docs>. Accessed: 2023-07-02.

UI updates and accelerate the development process by shortening iteration cycles⁹. Following a Model-View-ViewModel (MVVM) pattern is also recommended, ensuring a clear separation of concerns, enhancing maintainability, and promoting scalability [56]. These recommendations aim to optimize the app's future development for a seamless and maintainable user experience.

⁹Google. Flutter documentation. <https://docs.flutter.dev/>. Accessed: 2023-07-02.

5.3 User Interaction Flow

The interaction flow (as depicted in Figure 5) represents the proposed paths a user would follow, from launching the app to completing a run. It is designed to illustrate the decisions users would make and how the app would adapt based on their input and physiological data. The interaction flow remains conceptual, with the goal of showing how the system could provide dynamic and responsive feedback to enhance the user's running experience.

Conceptual Nature of the Design

It is essential to clarify that the features and systems described in this section are conceptual and have not been implemented. The proposed system architecture serves as a theoretical model for how such a system could be developed to enhance the running experience through real-time feedback and user interaction. Further research and development would be required to implement these features, validate the underlying algorithms, and test the system's effectiveness in practical settings.

5.3.1 Intuitive User Interface and Interaction

The interface of the "Run and Interact 2.0" app is designed with simplicity and minimalism in mind to ensure a seamless user experience while running. The primary goal is to reduce distractions and cognitive load, allowing users to focus on their performance rather than the device.

Home Screen: The interaction begins with a simple, visually clear home screen. Users are greeted with a prominent "Start Run" button to quickly initiate their activity. Additional features include a summary of previous runs that provides key statistics such as average pace, distance, and time. The user can also navigate to personalized settings from this screen.

Settings Screen: This screen offers deep customization options. Users can adjust breathing tempos, rhythms, and select from various soundscapes to match their desired running intensity and mood. The system also integrates with third-party music services to provide personalized playlists tailored to the runner's preferences.

Run Screen: Once the run begins, the interface transitions into the Run Screen. Unlike traditional running apps that overload users with visual data, this app shifts the focus from visual feedback to sound-based interaction. Personalized breathing cues, motivational music tracks, and real-time prompts guide runners through their activity. The screen itself displays minimal optional data, such as elapsed time and distance, but aims to keep the user's attention on the audio and the run itself.

Run Setup and Warm-up Phase: Prior to starting the run, users have the option to configure their run parameters through the "Run Setup" screen, selecting goals such as distance or pace. A "Warm-up Phase" is included, helping runners ease into their exercise routine. During this time, users can interact with the app through gestures or simple commands.

Voice Commands and Motion-based Controls: A key feature of the app is its use of voice commands and motion-based controls. Instead of requiring screen interaction during a run, runners can use voice commands to adjust settings or skip songs. Grounded in the principles of *embodied cognition*, this interaction design allows users to control the app using natural body movements or voice. By allowing users to control settings through physical gestures and voice commands, the app reduces cognitive load, helping runners remain present in the activity. This aligns with embodied cognition by making the interaction more intuitive and enhancing overall focus on running [34, 43].

5.3.2 Motion-Based Controls for Seamless Interaction

The motion-based controls would allow runners to interact with the app without needing to engage with the screen directly. By utilizing the device's accelerometer and gyroscope sensors, the app could detect specific gestures such as head tilts, taps, or wrist movements. These controls would enable users to change volume, skip tracks, or pause the run, providing a seamless, hands-free experience. The app would continuously monitor background sensor data at a 50Hz sampling rate to ensure quick responsiveness.

Accurate gesture recognition would be achieved through a machine learning model, trained on a diverse dataset of user movements [42]. This would ensure that the system works reliably in real-world running conditions. To enhance usability, the app would provide visual feedback confirming that gestures have been correctly recognized, boosting user confidence in the system.

This feature supports the app's focus on reducing cognitive load and distractions during runs, in line with *embodied cognition* principles, making interactions more intuitive and integrated with the runner's movements.

5.3.3 Flowchart

The user interaction flow reflects the logical steps users go through while using the "Run and Interact" version 2 app, from the moment they start the application to the completion of their run.

Figure 5: User interaction flowchart for "Run and Interact" app version 2.

The interaction flow begins with the Home Screen where users decide whether to start a new run, revisit past run statistics, or modify their settings. If they select a New Run, they are guided through a Run Setup phase where they can configure parameters like pace and distance. For more advanced users, there is a Quick Start option that allows them to jump directly to the Run Screen.

During the run, real-time feedback is provided through auditory prompts, voice commands, and motion-based controls. The flow also supports in-run adjustments, such as skipping tracks or altering pace settings through gestures. Once the run concludes, users enter the Post-Run phase where they can review their performance data and compare it with previous runs stored in the Run History Screen.

This structured interaction flow ensures that users have complete control over their run without being overwhelmed by unnecessary features or excessive visual data. It maintains focus on the running experience while providing subtle guidance throughout the process.

5.4 Personalized Sound-Based Guidance for Enhanced Performance

The proposed personalized sound-based guidance system is a central feature of *Run and Interact Version 2*. The app's Sound Engine would leverage scientifically supported breathing patterns to help runners synchronize their breath with their cadence, optimizing oxygen intake and reducing fatigue. For instance, a 2:2 inhale-to-exhale ratio could enhance running economy [7].

As a recommendation for future development, the Sound Engine would generate and deliver auditory feedback by combining native platform libraries with custom algorithms to provide users with real-time, responsive audio cues [1]. This engine can leverage pre-recorded sounds and synthesized tones to create personalized feedback for the user.

Breathing Patterns and Dynamic Adjustment

The breathing guidance module is a core feature of the app, providing users with rhythmic cues that synchronize with their running pace. Users can customize inhale and exhale durations and choose from pre-designed breathing patterns such as 2:2 or 4:4 ratios. The app calculates the time intervals required and triggers audio cues accordingly. Platform-specific timers and audio playback mechanisms ensure precise timing and responsiveness. The system combines pre-recorded sounds and synthesized tones to create various feedback types suited to different running conditions.

Breathing patterns refer to specific rhythmic cycles of inhaling and exhaling designed to improve running efficiency. For example, a 2:2 breathing ratio, meaning two steps per inhale and two steps per exhale, is commonly used for maintaining a steady pace.

The app adjusts these breathing patterns in real-time based on physiological data such as heart rate or pace. If the runner's heart rate exceeds a certain threshold, the app automatically modifies the breathing rhythm to encourage deeper, slower breaths, helping reduce fatigue and optimize oxygen intake. The app's Sound Engine synchronizes these adjustments with auditory cues, guiding the runner through the optimal breathing cadence.

This feature also includes guided breathwork sessions for focus, cool-down, and warm-up phases, using principles of mindfulness and concentration to improve performance and enhance the overall running experience [14].

5.4.1 Soundscapes: A Dynamic and Personalized Listening Experience

The Soundscapes feature would be designed to enhance the user's running experience by integrating with the device's music library. Users could create custom playlists by selecting tracks from their library or choose from a curated collection of binaural beats and ambient sounds, categorized by mood and intensity. The system would also offer suggestions based on real-time physiological data, such as heart rate, to match the intensity of the run.

A key feature of the Soundscapes system would be volume adjustment through motion-based gestures or on-screen sliders. By leveraging device sensors such as the accelerometer and gyro-

scope, users could adjust the volume by performing a simple double-tap gesture on their smart-watch, ensuring minimal distractions. The app would use an audio library plugin for robust and quick playback, ensuring seamless transitions between tracks and audio cues¹⁰.

Proposed as part of the personalized auditory experience, this feature aligns with the principles of *embodied cognition*, providing real-time feedback that adapts to the runner's physiological state.

5.5 Customizable Soundscapes and Motivational Cues

Run and Interact 2.0 app understands that different runners respond to different stimuli, so the soundscape can be significantly customized. Users can create their own playlists with motivational music tracks, binaural beats, or ambient sounds, or select from well-curated options. Motivational cues and messages can also be tailored by users to fit their preferences and goals. According to research, performance and enjoyment can be greatly impacted by the tempo and genre of music [30], and sound-based guidance should account for the emotional impact of sounds to enhance motivation and arouse positive feelings [18].

In addition, binaural beats could be used to sync with the runner's cadence or heart rate, offering an auditory stimulus that enhances mental focus and aids in achieving a flow state during the run. Research indicates that binaural beats can improve cognitive flexibility, attention, and memory by reducing mind-wandering and enhancing focus during physical activities [4, 25].

5.6 Speculative Auditory Cues for Enhanced Running Experience

Auditory cues are integral to the *Run and Interact Version 2*, guiding runners through different stages of their activity. These cues are categorized based on their relationship to the runner's movement and the type of information they convey. The app uses a combination of naturalistic and non-naturalistic sounds to deliver a personalized auditory experience.

- **Naturalistic Sounds:** These are sounds directly tied to the runner's movements or environment, such as footsteps or wind. They provide real-time feedback on pace and rhythm, offering a sense of immersion by aligning the runner's physical actions with the auditory cues.
- **Non-Naturalistic Sounds:** These sounds communicate information or prompt specific responses. They can be further divided into the following types:
 1. **Semantic/Metaphorical Sounds:** These are symbolic cues, such as a rising pitch to signify increasing speed or a chime to indicate an upcoming turn.
 2. **Sonification:** This converts data into sound. For instance, tones can signal changes in heart rate or pace, offering continuous real-time feedback.

¹⁰Mehmet Fatih Simsek. just audio: A Flutter audio plugin. https://pub.dev/packages/just_audio. Accessed: 2023-07-02.

3. **Non-Arbitrary Associations:** These sounds have learned meanings, such as a beep marking the start or end of a run, providing clear signals for key moments during the activity.
4. **Artificial Sounds:** These are synthetic cues designed to be easily recognizable, providing important information even without inherent meaning.

The *Run and Interact Version 2* could integrate these types of cues to create a holistic, tailored auditory guidance. Rhythmic breathing patterns could help runners set their pace, while motivational music and custom cues enhance both enjoyment and focus during their run.

5.7 Gamified Features for User Engagement and Tracking

As a feature aimed at fostering ongoing engagement and motivation, *Run and Interact Version 2* integrates gamification elements such as points, badges, levels, challenges, and rewards. These components leverage users' intrinsic desire for accomplishment and progress, aligning with self-determination theory, which emphasizes competence, autonomy, and relatedness in fostering motivation [16]. For example, the app could award points for each completed run, allowing users to unlock new levels or badges. Challenges may encourage users to achieve personal records or reach community-wide goals, while rewards for consistent participation could promote long-term engagement.

These gamification features, including badges, points, and challenges, foster motivation by providing a sense of competence (through achievements), autonomy (through goal-setting), and relatedness (through community participation), aligning with self-determination theory [16]. Incorporating these elements, the app aims to make running a more enjoyable and rewarding experience, boosting adherence and encouraging behavior change over time.

In the next section, we will explore design suggestions that aim to further refine and optimize the *Run and Interact Version 2* app. These suggestions provide a strategic framework to ensure that the app continues to meet the evolving needs of users, enhancing their overall experience and engagement.

6 Design Suggestions

The following section outlines key design suggestions for the *Run and Interact* 2.0 app. These recommendations aim to enhance user experience, improve functionality, and ensure a personalized, intuitive running experience through seamless integration with wearables and user-centered design. This section also explores future directions for the app to meet evolving user needs.

6.1 User Interface Design and User Experience

Run and Interact 2.0 app maintains a simple and minimalistic user interface (UI) to ensure that runners experience minimal distractions during their activities. The design follows established UI/UX principles, such as consistent navigation patterns, intuitive controls, and a clear visual hierarchy [58]. The app's interface prioritizes usability by reducing cognitive load and visual strain.

The UI uses simple-to-read fonts and a soothing color palette to create a stress-free environment for the user. Moreover, the UI elements are designed to be accessible and operable even when users have sweaty or gloved fingers. Along with quick access to personalized settings, playlists, and recent run history, the home screen features a prominent "Start Run" button. The run screen focuses primarily on delivering auditory feedback and minimizes the amount of visual data displayed during a run, showing only essential metrics like pace and distance.

Users can easily access the settings screen to adjust soundscapes, breathing patterns, and motion-based controls. A tutorial section provides interactive displays and explanations of the app's various features, ensuring that users can fully understand and leverage the app's functionality.

6.2 Integration with Wearable Devices

Run and Interact 2.0 app seamlessly integrates with a variety of wearable devices, such as smartwatches and heart rate monitors, using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology. This integration allows the app to collect real-time physiological data, such as heart rate and pace, which can be used to personalize breathing guidance and soundscapes based on the runner's current condition. BLE technology is widely known for its low power consumption and reliable wireless data transmission in wearable devices¹¹.

These wearables include popular brands like Fitbit, Garmin, and Apple Watch, ensuring broad compatibility with devices that runners commonly use. Future updates could expand compatibility with other fitness trackers and smart gear, further enhancing the app's versatility and usability across different platforms.

¹¹For more on BLE technology, see: Kyle R. Mallires et al., "Mitigation of Data Packet Loss in Bluetooth Low Energy-Based Wearable Healthcare Ecosystem," *Biosensors* 2021, 11(10), 350, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios11100350>.

Wearable integration ensures that users can monitor their performance in real-time, with data directly influencing the feedback provided by the app. For example, the app can adjust breathing cues and soundscapes in response to heart rate changes to keep the user within their optimal performance zone. Additionally, Run and Interact 2.0 supports offline mode, allowing users to continue using the app's core features even if their wearable devices lose connection temporarily.

As wearable technology continues to evolve, future iterations of the app could explore even more advanced integrations, including smart clothing or shoes that provide real-time feedback on running form, cadence, and other metrics. This expansion would provide greater accessibility and utility for a broader range of users, making the app a comprehensive tool for both novice and experienced runners.

6.3 Overview of Screen Designs and Functionalities

The following design recommendations aim to enhance the functionality and user experience of the *Run and Interact* Version 2 app, referred to as ***Breathe and Run*** in the UI designs for a more intuitive user-facing identity. Each screen has been carefully crafted to ensure simplicity, ease of use, and personalization, allowing runners to adapt the app to their unique preferences and goals. By integrating principles of user-centered design and leveraging real-time feedback from wearable devices, *Breathe and Run* provides a seamless and intuitive experience for runners of all levels. The subsequent screens demonstrate how the app prioritizes customization, accessibility, and real-time data integration, ensuring that users can effortlessly tailor their breathing guidance, music selection, and feedback systems to optimize performance. Below, we present a detailed analysis of each screen and its role in supporting the app's core functions.

6.3.1 Personalized Breathing Guidance

Figure 6: Personalized breathing guidance screen.

The first suggested UI screen of the "Breathe and Run" app introduces the feature for personalized breathing guidance. This screen highlights two rhythmic breathing patterns: the 2:2 rhythm, which instructs users to inhale for 2 steps and exhale for 2 steps, and the 4:4 rhythm, which extends the inhale and exhale durations to 4 steps each. These breathing patterns are designed to sync a runner's breath with their movement, enhancing oxygen intake and reducing fatigue, key principles backed by research in breathing techniques for endurance sports. The user interface (UI) is simple, featuring clear visual cues and a streamlined layout that ensures ease of use even during physical activity. Users can choose to begin a guided run or select a "Quick Start" option, ensuring flexibility in how they engage with the app.

The emphasis on breathing guidance aligns with theories of embodied cognition, where the body's natural movements, such as breathing, are synchronized with external stimuli like auditory cues to optimize performance. By offering multiple breathing rhythm options, the app caters to runners of different skill levels and preferences. Additionally, users have the flexibility to customize their rhythmic breathing patterns, ensuring that the guidance fits their individual needs and running styles. The clean, minimalistic design reduces cognitive load, ensuring users remain focused on their running and breathing without being overwhelmed by interface elements.

6.3.2 Start Run and Guided Breathing

Figure 7: Personalized breathing patterns and auditory feedback options.

The second screen of the "Breathe and Run" app provides users with a selection of rhythmic breathing patterns and auditory feedback options to personalize their running experience. It showcases three breathing rhythms—2:2, 4:4, and 5:5—each indicating different step-based inhale and exhale durations. These options allow users to align their breathing with their running cadence, helping optimize oxygen intake and reduce fatigue. This flexibility in rhythm selection ensures that runners of varying experience levels can tailor the app's guidance to their specific needs.

Additionally, the app offers multiple auditory feedback styles, such as metronome, voice guidance, and nature sounds. These choices help create a customized auditory environment that can enhance focus and performance. The simplified layout and clear visual cues emphasize ease of use, allowing users to adjust their settings quickly before starting a run. This screen highlights the app's focus on personalization and its ability to cater to individual user preferences, ensuring an immersive and engaging running experience.

6.3.3 Breathing Patterns

Figure 8: Breathing pattern options with customization for personalized running guidance.

The third screen of the "Breathe and Run" app offers users a variety of breathing patterns to choose from, such as 4-2-4, 3-3, 4-4, and 5-5, each tailored to different running intensities and goals. The breathing patterns include specific inhalation and exhalation steps, with some rhythms designed for more controlled and paced breathing (like 4-2-4, where users hold their breath for two steps after inhaling). This flexibility allows runners to match their breathing with the effort level of their run, improving efficiency and oxygen intake.

The customization option enhances the user experience by allowing personalization of the breathing patterns, ensuring that each runner can adjust the app to their specific needs. Whether a beginner or an experienced runner, this feature offers a versatile approach to breathing exercises during runs. Additionally, users can select the style of auditory feedback (e.g., metronome, voice guidance, or nature sounds), providing an immersive, adaptive experience that further optimizes performance.

6.3.4 Inhale/Exhale Duration Customization

Figure 9: Breathing pattern customization screen with dynamic inhale/exhale adjustment options.

The fourth screen of the "Breathe and Run" app allows users to select a breathing pattern that best suits their running style and goals. This customizable breathing guide ensures users can adjust the inhale/exhale duration according to their preferences. The options range from common patterns like the 4:4 ratio, where the runner inhales and exhales over four steps, to more advanced patterns like the 6:2 ratio, offering a greater degree of customization for seasoned runners. Users can increment or decrement the inhale/exhale ratio by using the simple "+" or "-" buttons, ensuring that adjustments are easy to make, even on the go.

The flexibility of this design supports a user-centered approach, allowing runners to experiment with different breathing patterns and find what works best for them. By adjusting breathing rhythms dynamically, runners can optimize their breathing technique based on personal needs, pace, and running environment. This level of customization is particularly beneficial for different fitness levels, from beginners to advanced athletes.

6.3.5 Breathe and Run Settings

Figure 10: Settings screen for adjusting auditory cues and connecting a heart rate monitor in the Breathe and Run app.

This screen acts as the settings hub for the "Breathe and Run" app, giving users control over auditory cues and the option to connect a heart rate monitor. It highlights the app's emphasis on customization. The "Auditory Cues" section allows users to adjust volume and select between guided breathing, which syncs breathing to running pace, or nature sounds for a more relaxed workout background.

This flexibility lets users tailor the experience to their needs. Guided breathing is ideal for pacing, while nature sounds offer a less structured option. The "Heart Rate Monitor" option showcases Bluetooth integration, enabling real-time heart rate data to adjust breathing cues and improve efficiency.

The interface is simple and user-friendly, with large buttons and minimal text, ensuring easy adjustments even during a run. The "Confirm" button allows users to save their settings quickly. This screen embodies the app's user-centered approach, ensuring runners of all levels benefit from tailored guidance.

6.3.6 Running with Music

Figure 11: Breathe and Run app’s curated soundscapes and music playlist options for personalized running experiences.

This screen introduces the music and soundscapes feature of the "Breathe and Run" app. It shows a curated playlist called "Run with the Wind," allowing users to create an optimal running environment with tailored soundscapes and playlists. The app provides three distinct options for users: a "Running Playlist" with a runtime of over three hours, as well as "Morning Soundscapes" and "Evening Soundscapes," which are intended to complement different phases of the user's daily schedule. These playlists can help runners stay motivated, focused, or relaxed, depending on the sounds selected. Users can easily customize or create new playlists to suit their preferences by selecting the "Create New" option at the bottom of the screen.

By offering customizable playlists, the app adapts to different runner needs and preferences, supporting diverse training environments. Music has been shown to positively affect mood and performance during exercise, which is why integrating personalized soundscapes aligns with theories of embodied cognition and user-centered design. Through auditory cues and soundscapes, runners can maintain their rhythm, focus, and enjoyment throughout their workout.

6.3.7 Connect to Spotify or Apple Music

Figure 12: Connect to popular music services for a seamless running experience with personalized playlists.

This screen demonstrates the connectivity options available in the "Breathe and Run" app, where users can link their favorite music streaming services, such as Spotify, Apple Music, YouTube Music, Deezer, and Tidal, to enhance their running sessions. By integrating with popular music platforms, the app offers a seamless experience, allowing runners to enjoy personalized playlists without switching between apps. Whether users prefer upbeat tracks for motivation or calming soundscapes for mindfulness, the app supports various music preferences tailored to each runner's style and needs.

The ability to connect directly to multiple music services simplifies the setup process, ensuring that runners can focus on their performance rather than manually searching for tracks during a workout. This feature is particularly useful for those who rely on specific music genres or playlists to match the intensity of their runs. The interface design is clean and straightforward, with clear navigation options, allowing users to quickly connect to their music services with just a tap.

6.3.8 Connecting a Wearable

Figure 13: Connect Your Wearables screen offering device management and heart rate zone customization for a more personalized running experience.

This screen allows users to manage their connection to wearable devices, such as smartwatches or fitness trackers, which can provide real-time physiological data during their run. The interface offers an intuitive "Scan for Devices" option, making it easy for users to connect their preferred wearable. Once connected, the device (e.g., a Fitbit Charge 5) displays as "Connected," while others remain available for pairing. Below, the "Zone" feature offers a customizable heart rate zone system, where users can select from easy, moderate, or hard zones based on their fitness goals or the intensity of their workout.

The customization continues with the option to change the heart rate zones, allowing the app to provide more accurate feedback in line with the user's physical condition. The "Troubleshoot Issues" section ensures that users can resolve any problems with device connections or heart rate monitoring, ensuring a smooth experience while using the app.

6.3.9 Post-Run Feedback

✕ **Post-run feedback**

Share your thoughts on today's run

Your feedback will help us improve Breathe and Run.

Satisfaction scale

3
★★☆☆☆
1.2k reviews

5	20%
4	20%
3	30%
2	20%
1	10%

Usability scale

3
★★☆☆☆
1.2k reviews

5	20%
4	20%
3	30%
2	20%
1	10%

Open-ended questions

What did you like about the run?

What can we do better?

Submit

Figure 14: The post-run feedback screen encourages user engagement by collecting ratings and open-ended suggestions for improving the app's usability and overall experience.

This screen collects essential post-run feedback from users, helping the developers of *Breathe and Run* continuously refine and improve the app's functionality. It is divided into three main sections: the satisfaction scale, the usability scale, and open-ended questions. The satisfaction scale allows users to rate their overall enjoyment of the run, while the usability scale focuses on the app's ease of use during the running session. These ratings, displayed in a star format, are supplemented with a breakdown of user reviews, providing additional context for future app adjustments. The open-ended questions offer an opportunity for users to provide detailed feedback, discussing what they liked about the run and suggesting areas for improvement. The layout is simple and user-friendly, allowing users to easily and quickly share their thoughts.

This feedback system not only provides valuable data for iterative improvements but also encourages consistent user engagement. Runners feel that their input directly influences the development process, fostering a sense of contribution and ownership. This community-driven approach ensures that the app evolves based on real-world user experiences, addressing both general usability and specific user needs.

The post-run feedback system is critical for the app's ongoing development. By capturing real user experiences, the app can better align its features with runner expectations, thereby enhancing overall user satisfaction and functionality. Furthermore, this system reinforces the app's user-centered design, ensuring that future updates are informed by genuine user input, making the app more responsive to its community's needs.

6.3.10 Run Summary Screen

Figure 15: A detailed breakdown of the runner's performance metrics, helping users assess their workout and track their progress over time.

This screen summarizes the key statistics of the user's run, offering an in-depth overview of their performance. Displaying metrics such as distance covered, time spent, average pace, calories burned, breaths per minute, and consistency, it allows the user to reflect on their workout. This data not only helps runners assess their progress but also encourages them to aim for improvement in future runs. The "Save Run" button ensures that this information is stored for long-term tracking and comparison. Additionally, the option to share results or start a new run immediately after finishing creates a seamless flow from one activity to the next. The design emphasizes clarity and functionality, ensuring that all important data is easy to understand and readily accessible.

The clean and minimalist design of the screen ensures that users can quickly absorb their performance metrics without feeling overwhelmed. Buttons are clearly labeled, and the visual hierarchy ensures that the most important information—distance, time, and pace—are prominently displayed. The summary enhances user engagement by allowing them to reflect on their physical output and set goals for future runs.

6.3.11 Progress Tracking

Figure 16: Progress tracking screen displaying the runner's breathing metrics over time.

This Progress Tracking screen provides users with a comprehensive view of their breathing performance over time, offering key insights to help optimize future runs. The screen tracks multiple metrics, including the average "Breaths Per Minute" (BPM) and breathing consistency, while also measuring improvements in breathing rates over the last 30 days. Each metric is displayed as a visual trend line, allowing runners to compare their progress week by week. For example, the BPM section shows how many breaths a runner takes per minute, with the app indicating a percentage improvement (or decline) over the past month.

The "Consistency" metric represents how regularly the user adheres to their breathing patterns during runs, which is a critical factor for maintaining efficiency and reducing fatigue. By maintaining consistent breathing, users can optimize oxygen intake, improving stamina and overall performance. The "Improvements" section measures the reduction in breathing rate over time, an indication that the user is becoming more efficient, needing fewer breaths to maintain their performance levels. Such feedback empowers runners by giving them clear, actionable data on how to improve, ultimately supporting a more personalized and effective training regimen. This screen also emphasizes ease of use by including a "Start New Session" button at the bottom, allowing users to quickly jump back into a new run while maintaining focus on improving these metrics. The integration of breathing-related data aligns with the app's core goal of leveraging embodied cognition—using bodily rhythms like breathing to enhance running performance. Over time, users can see tangible improvements in their breathing, which can translate to better endurance, less fatigue, and faster recovery after workouts.

7 Discussion

7.1 Discussion of Findings

While preliminary, the results of the evaluation reveal new insights into the potential of the *Run and Interact* 2.0 app (as mentioned in the previous chapter on *Breathe and Run* for an intuitive user experience) for enhancing the running experience through customization, real-time feedback, and embodied cognition principles. These findings contribute significantly to the growing body of research on the use of digital tools in exercise contexts, particularly regarding how personalized guidance can impact runner performance, focus, and overall experience.

The positive feedback on personalized breathing guidance reflects the emphasis on customization in exercise apps, which has been widely acknowledged as a factor in user satisfaction and effectiveness in existing literature [20]. Customizable features such as inhale/exhale patterns and soundscapes cater to individual preferences and training needs, allowing users to optimize their running experience. This ability to cater to individual variability is key, as demonstrated by Janssen et al. [27], who underscore the importance of flexibility and user control in technology-supported exercise routines.

7.2 Addressing Research Questions

RQ1: How can refinements to a sound-based breathing app prototype improve runners' focus and perceived ease of use?

The evaluation demonstrated that personalized breathing guidance, such as the ability to customize inhale/exhale patterns, significantly improved participants' focus and ease of use. The real-time guidance helped runners maintain a controlled pace, enhancing their focus during running sessions. Consistent with the literature on auditory feedback in sports, runners noted how such guidance helped them remain focused on their breathing rhythm, which, in turn, improved their running experience [7, 20]. However, some feedback indicated that users desired even more control over soundscapes and feedback systems, suggesting that future refinements could further improve ease of use and user satisfaction.

RQ2: How does iterative design impact the usability and effectiveness of various interaction methods?

The iterative design process of *Run and Interact* app version 2 allowed for the continuous refinement of the interaction methods. Motion-based controls were generally well-received by participants but faced accuracy challenges during high-intensity runs. These challenges highlight the need for improving gesture recognition algorithms, particularly for fast-paced activities. The findings suggest that while the iterative design enhanced usability, particularly for screen-based and sound interaction, the motion-based controls require further optimization to ensure

consistent performance during different running conditions. Previous studies on motion-based controls also highlight similar challenges in virtual environments, emphasizing the importance of refining these methods for real-world application [32].

RQ3: How can interaction design principles and theories of embodied cognition inform the development of motion-based and hybrid interaction methods for a running context?

The app's integration of motion-based controls and real-time auditory feedback aligns with the principles of embodied cognition, which posit that external stimuli (such as sound) can synchronize with body movements to enhance performance. By synchronizing breathing rhythms with steps and using sound cues, the app effectively incorporates embodied cognition to improve runners' focus and reduce perceived exertion [2]. Participants found that these features helped them stay in rhythm with their movements, allowing for a more intuitive running experience. However, further exploration of how embodied cognition can be leveraged more deeply in future iterations—such as offering more responsive feedback systems—will likely yield even greater benefits.

7.3 Motion-Based Controls and Usability

Another important finding from the study is the positive reception of motion-based controls, which allowed runners to interact with the app using natural body movements. This reflects broader trends in the usability of motion-based interaction methods in fitness apps, which have shown promise in reducing the need for visual engagement with a device during exercise [32]. However, participants did report some accuracy issues with these controls, particularly during faster runs. These challenges highlight the need for improving gesture recognition algorithms, a point also raised by Goudsmit and Vos in their 2021 study on motion-based interaction [23].

7.4 Perceived Exertion and Enjoyment

The study also indicated that participants perceived a reduction in exertion when using the app's guided breathing features. For example, one runner noted feeling “less out of breath,” while another mentioned that the app helped them maintain a “more controlled pace.” These subjective reports align with research on the benefits of rhythmic breathing for physical performance. According to Brick et al. [10], rhythmic breathing has been shown to reduce the perception of effort during exercise, leading to improved performance and greater endurance.

This reduction in perceived exertion, coupled with the app's customizable features, enhanced participants' overall enjoyment of their runs. The ability to tailor soundscapes and breathing rhythms to individual preferences was a key factor in this enjoyment, as it allowed runners to feel more in control of their experience. This reflects broader trends in the design of exercise apps, where personalization is increasingly recognized as essential to maintaining user engagement and motivation [20].

7.5 Customization and User Preferences

While the feedback on real-time data and auditory cues was generally positive, some participants found the real-time data distracting, highlighting the need for more customizable feedback options. This variability in user preferences underscores the importance of flexibility in the design of fitness applications. Future iterations of the Run and Interact 2.0 app should offer greater control over the type and amount of feedback users receive, allowing them to customize their experience according to their needs and preferences. This recommendation is consistent with Menheere et al.'s work on the role of personalization in user satisfaction with digital fitness tools [41].

7.6 Project-Specific Challenges and Difficulties

Several challenges were encountered during the course of the project, both practical and academic. Initially, getting familiar with the scope of the larger Run and Interact project posed difficulties, as it required a comprehensive understanding of interdisciplinary goals between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and sports science. Although I had some foundational knowledge from a course on HCI research projects, this was my first time engaging in independent academic writing, which made structuring and refining the thesis particularly challenging.

The practical aspects of the project also presented difficulties. While working part-time at a tech company in Salzburg, balancing these responsibilities with commuting to the RIF (Sport Science) center for user tests created logistical challenges. This, along with maintaining progress on the thesis and participating in the main project in Salzburg, required careful time management. Additionally, finding suitable test users who met the specific criteria for the study proved to be time-consuming and complicated the scheduling of user tests.

One of the most significant ongoing challenges was managing the iterative process of developing the thesis. This involved regularly submitting drafts and receiving detailed feedback from the supervisor, which required substantial revisions after each round of review. While this process was demanding, it significantly improved key skills such as critical thinking, academic writing, and the ability to refine and narrow research questions. Each revision sharpened the focus of the thesis, aligning it more closely with the research goals and the supervisor's expectations.

Moreover, language barriers during user testing added complexity, as several participants spoke German, and my proficiency in the language was limited. This required me to adapt my communication methods during testing, which, in turn, improved my ability to work in multilingual environments. The broad scope of the project further complicated matters, initially making it difficult to focus on key objectives. However, through the continuous revision process and feedback from my supervisor, I developed a stronger ability to streamline the narrative and define clear research aims. These challenges ultimately shaped my approach to research and collaboration, equipping me with valuable skills for future academic and professional projects.

7.7 Limitations of the Study

There are several limitations to the current study that must be considered when interpreting these findings:

- **Small Sample Size:** The limited number of participants in the study restricts the generalizability of the results. A larger, more diverse sample would provide a broader understanding of how the Run and Interact 2.0 app performs across different demographics and fitness levels.
- **Controlled Environment:** The study was conducted on a running track, which may not fully represent real-world running conditions. In real-world settings, runners are exposed to varying terrains, weather conditions, and environmental distractions that could affect their interaction with the app. Future studies should test the app in more diverse running environments to assess its performance under natural conditions.
- **Lack of a Control Group:** Without a control group, it is difficult to isolate the specific effects of the app from other variables that may have influenced the participants' experience. Introducing a control group in future studies would allow for a more rigorous evaluation of the app's impact on running performance and user satisfaction.
- **Project-Specific Challenges:** In addition to the academic hurdles mentioned above, coordinating with supervisor, managing the project timeline, and adjusting to changes in research scope due to relocations and other commitments were key challenges during the study.

7.8 Summary of Key Findings and Broader Impact

The evaluation provides promising insights into the *Run and Interact 2.0* app's potential to enhance the running experience through personalized breathing guidance, real-time feedback, and motion-based controls. While there were some usability challenges, particularly regarding the accuracy of gesture recognition, the app's customization features were well-received, and participants reported improvements in focus, enjoyment, and perceived exertion.

The broader impact of these findings suggests that future running apps could benefit from deeper personalization features, allowing users to fully customize their feedback systems and interaction methods. Additionally, motion-based controls present a promising direction for future development, offering an intuitive method of interaction that reduces the need for visual engagement with a device while running. Incorporating real-time feedback and motion-based interaction methods could lead to the design of more immersive and effective fitness technologies.

8 Conclusion and Future Directions

8.1 Conclusion

This thesis investigated the design and evaluation of "Run and Interact" 2.0 app, a sound-based running guidance app aimed at enhancing focus, enjoyment, and performance through personalized interaction and customization. The research findings underscore the potential of sound-based interventions to improve the running experience, particularly through auditory feedback, motion-based control, and individualized features.

The iterative design process, informed by user feedback and a comprehensive literature review, led to the development of a prototype app integrating motion-based controls, personalized breathing patterns, and customizable soundscapes. Initial evaluations indicate that these elements positively impact runners' focus and enjoyment, with potential benefits for performance as well. However, further refinement and research are essential to optimize the app's functionality and address areas such as motion-based control accuracy and soundscape diversity.

Future work will involve refining the app's design and conducting extensive user studies in real-world settings. Key areas of future research include investigating the long-term effects of "Run and Interact" 02 on performance, motivation, and adherence to running routines. Additionally, exploring integrations with other wearable technologies, such as smartwatches and GPS trackers, will allow for a more comprehensive and personalized running experience. There is also significant potential to explore additional modalities, such as haptic feedback and augmented reality, to further enhance the runner's experience.

The insights gained from this research can inform the design of future sound-based interventions in athletics and contribute to the broader field of technology-mediated physical activity. Understanding how runners interact with and benefit from such guidance tools can help shape the future of fitness technologies, offering more immersive, enjoyable, and effective tools for athletes.

In summary, this thesis demonstrates the potential of sound-based interaction and personalized customization to create a more immersive, enjoyable, and effective running experience. "Run and Interact" 2.0 app is a promising first step toward leveraging technology to support runners in achieving their goals. With continued research and development, this area holds the potential to revolutionize the way athletes engage with technology in their training and performance optimization.

8.2 Evaluation and Future Run and Interact 2.0 App Directions

The *Run and Interact 2.0* app will undergo continuous improvement through user feedback and research, ensuring that it evolves to meet the needs of runners across different skill levels and environments. The app will include integrated feedback collection mechanisms, such as in-app surveys and post-run feedback forms, to assess its effectiveness and usability.

These mechanisms will help collect valuable user data, which will drive the iterative improvement of the app's features. Future studies will focus on determining the best combination of auditory cues and feedback for different user preferences, along with testing the app in various running conditions. Furthermore, the app could provide auditory feedback on running form—such as foot strike patterns and cadence—based on real-time sensor data from wearable devices. This feature could also support injury prevention by encouraging optimal running form.

While Run and Interact app version 2 has the potential to enhance the running experience, some limitations need to be addressed. For instance, auditory feedback may not be suitable for users with hearing impairments, and the current prototype may not fully reflect the diverse needs of the running community. Future studies will explore alternative feedback methods, such as haptic feedback, and conduct more extensive testing in diverse environments. Additionally, the app could integrate with emerging running technologies, including augmented reality headsets, to create a more immersive experience.

Future directions also include exploring how augmented reality (AR) could offer visual cues in addition to auditory feedback. By integrating AR glasses, runners could visualize real-time data such as pace or heart rate in their field of vision, further reducing the need for visual engagement with the app. Likewise, integration with wearables such as smart shoes could provide haptic feedback for more precise running form adjustments, contributing to injury prevention and enhanced training outcomes.

The app's continuous improvement will rely on user-centered design frameworks and feedback mechanisms to ensure that it adapts to the changing needs of runners [44].

8.2.1 Future Research Directions

Building on the insights gained from this research, several avenues for future investigation can further refine the app and expand its applicability. These include:

- **Expanding User Base and Context:** Conducting larger-scale studies in real-world running environments to assess the app's effectiveness across diverse demographics and conditions.
- **Longitudinal Studies:** Investigating the long-term impact of the app on running performance, motivation, and adherence to exercise routines.
- **Integration with Wearables:** Exploring the integration of the app with other wearable technologies, such as smartwatches and GPS trackers, to provide a more comprehensive and personalized running experience.

- **Implementation and Evaluation:** Implementing the proposed design recommendations and conducting user tests to gather feedback on the usability and performance of the updated app.
- **Physiological Impact:** Investigating the specific physiological mechanisms through which the app's features influence the running experience, using measures like heart rate variability and electrodermal activity.
- **Qualitative Exploration:** Employing qualitative research techniques, such as focus groups and in-depth interviews, to gain a deeper understanding of users' subjective experiences and motivations when using the app.

These future research directions will contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the app's impact and guide further refinements to enhance its effectiveness and user experience.

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References

- [1] Aurelius Aure and Marek Prochazka. “AudioKit: A Powerful Open-Source Audio Synthesis, Processing, and Analysis Platform for iOS”. In: *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*. 2015.
- [2] Christopher Baber. *Embodying Design: An Applied Science of Radical Embodied Cognition*. English. MIT Press, 2022, p. 212. ISBN: 9780262543781, 0262543788.
- [3] Brian P Bailey and Joseph A Konstan. “On the need for attention-aware systems: Measuring effects of interruption on task performance, error rate, and affective state”. In: *Computers in Human Behavior* 22.4 (2006), pp. 685–708. DOI: 10.1016/j.chb.2005.09.008.
- [4] S. Basu and B. Banerjee. “Potential of binaural beats intervention for improving memory and attention: insights from meta-analysis and systematic review”. In: *Psychological Research* (2022), pp. 467–479.
- [5] Christine Bauer, Anna Kratschmar, and Florian ‘Floyd’ Mueller. “Designing a Music-controlled Running Application: a Sports Science and Psychological Perspective”. In: *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. CHI ’15. Seoul, Republic of Korea: Association for Computing Machinery, 2015. ISBN: 9781450331852. DOI: 10.1145/2702123.2702241. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702241>.
- [6] Tao Bi et al. “Understanding the Shared Experiences of Runners and Spectators in Long-Distance Running Events”. In: *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. CHI ’19. Glasgow, Scotland Uk: Association for Computing Machinery, 2019. ISBN: 9781450359702. DOI: 10.1145/3290605.3300461. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300461>.
- [7] Marco Bigliassi et al. “Real-Time Auditory Feedback Improves Running Performance by Reducing Ground Reaction Force Impacts”. In: *Frontiers in Physiology* 10 (2019), p. 1150. DOI: 10.3389/fphys.2019.01150.
- [8] Rosie Borchert. “The 9 Best Running Apps of 2024”. In: *BarBend* (Jan. 2024). Accessed on 8 May 2024. <https://barbend.com/best-running-apps/>. URL: <https://barbend.com/best-running-apps/>.
- [9] Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke. “Using thematic analysis in psychology”. In: *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3.2 (2006), pp. 77–101. DOI: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.
- [10] Nicholas E Brick et al. “Effects of respiration pacing on kinematics and muscle activation during treadmill running”. In: *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport* 17.2 (2014), pp. 204–208. DOI: 10.1016/j.jsams.2013.09.001.
- [11] Yi-Ting Chen, Wei-Chen Liao, and Yi-Hsuan Wang. “Enhancing Running Exercise With IoT, Blockchain, and HR Adaptive Running Music”. In: *IEEE Access*. Vol. 12. IEEE, 2024, pp. 14173–14179. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3355792.

- [12] Andy Clark. *Being There: Putting Brain, Body, and World Together Again*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1997.
- [13] Christine Clermont et al. “Runners’ Perspectives on Wearable Technology for Injury Prevention”. In: *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 36.1 (2020), pp. 31–40. DOI: 10.1080/10447318.2019.1597575.
- [14] Lorenza S. Colzato, Wery P. M. van den Wildenberg, and Helen Zech. “Effects of Mindfulness Practice on Performance-Relevant Parameters and Performance Outcomes in Sports: A Meta-Analytical Review”. In: *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology* 29.1 (2017), pp. 3–28. DOI: 10.1080/10413200.2016.1146575.
- [15] Nelson Cowan et al. “Music for Exercise: A Review”. In: *Sports Medicine - Open* 7.1 (2021), p. 33. DOI: 10.1186/s40798-021-00335-9. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8167645/>.
- [16] Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan. “Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being”. In: *American Psychologist* 55.1 (2000), pp. 68–78.
- [17] Colin K. Drummond, Beth Lewandowski, and Carlo Massaroni. *Wearable Technology for Human Performance*. Accessed: 2024-09-09. 2021. URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/20640/wearable-technology-for-human-performance>.
- [18] Judy Edworthy, Stephanie Reid, and Shirley McDougall. “The Emotional Impact of Auditory Alarms in Critical Care: A Systematic Review”. In: *Human Factors* 65.1 (2023), pp. 142–162.
- [19] Paul Elvers. “Listening to empowering music: Effects on self-esteem and the state of flow”. In: *Musicae Scientiae* 20.3 (2016), pp. 410–426. DOI: 10.1177/1029864915625187.
- [20] David Firth, Costas I. Karageorghis, and Sally Clift. “Effects of Motivational Music on Physical Activity and Psychological Health Outcomes of Exercise App Users”. In: *Psychology of Sport and Exercise* 27 (2016), pp. 137–145. DOI: 10.1016/j.psychsport.2016.07.010.
- [21] Thomas H Fritz et al. “Synchronizing movements with music: Neural basis, performance benefits, and clinical implications”. In: *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1252.1 (2013), pp. 102–118. DOI: 10.1111/nyas.12029.
- [22] Jos Goudsmit and Steven Vos. “Exploring Feedback and Instruction Modalities using Low Fidelity Prototypes for Running: Towards Designing a Wearable System”. In: *European Conference on Cognitive Ergonomics (ECCE)*. Eindhoven, Netherlands: ACM, 2021, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1145/3452853.3452861. URL: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/fullHtml/10.1145/3452853.3452861>.
- [23] Sander Goudsmit and Steven Vos. “The Use of Wearable Fitness Trackers and Smartwatches Among Runners: A Study of User Motivations, Experiences, and Barriers to Use”. In: *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 37.19 (2021), pp. 1775–1791. DOI: 10.1080/10447318.2021.1923614.

- [24] Stephen Haffenberg. “A Review on the Relationship Between Sound and Movement in Sports and Rehabilitation”. In: *Sports Medicine* 41.4 (2011), pp. 281–293. DOI: 10.2165/11538670-000000000-00000.
- [25] B. Hommel et al. “High-frequency binaural beats increase cognitive flexibility: evidence from dual-task crosstalk”. In: *Frontiers in Psychology* 7 (2016), p. 1287.
- [26] Robert Jacobson. *Information Design*. Includes contributions by: Elizabeth Andersen, Judy Anderson, Simon Birrell, Mike Cooley, Brenda Dervin, Jim Gasperini, Yvonne M. Hansen, Steve Holtzman, Robert E. Horn, John Krygier, Sheryl Macy, Romedi Passini, Jef Raskin, Chandler Screven, Nathan Shedroff, Hal Thwaites, Roger Whitehouse. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, Aug. 2000, p. 373. ISBN: 978-0-262-10086-4.
- [27] Marijn Janssen et al. “Understanding different types of recreational runners and how they use running-related technology”. In: *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing and Proceedings of the 2017 ACM International Symposium on Wearable Computers*. ACM. 2017, pp. 817–822. DOI: 10.1145/3102123.3102362.
- [28] Mads Møller Jensen and Florian ‘Floyd’ Mueller. “Running with technology: Where are we heading?” In: *Proceedings of the 26th Australian Computer-Human Interaction Conference on Designing Futures: The Future of Design - OzCHI ’14*. 2014, pp. 527–530. ISBN: 9781450306539. DOI: 10.1145/2686612.2686696.
- [29] M. J. Johnson and N. K. Archibald. “Haptic feedback for enhancing interaction in virtual environments”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Haptics* 9.4 (2016), pp. 454–464.
- [30] Costas I. Karageorghis and David-Lee Priest. “Music in the Exercise Domain: A Review and Synthesis (Part I)”. In: *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology* 1.1 (2008), pp. 44–66. DOI: 10.1080/17509840701783331.
- [31] Iris Katz and Miri Assaf. “The effects of technological advancements on attention”. In: *Technology and attention in the digital age* (2018), pp. 205–222.
- [32] Jungwon Kim and Gangseong Lee. “Effects of Auditory and Visual Feedback on Motor Learning and Performance in a Virtual Reality-Based Running Simulation”. In: *Frontiers in Virtual Reality* 3 (2022), p. 748501. DOI: 10.3389/frvir.2022.748501.
- [33] Taesun Kim, Winston Chiu, and Mei Kei F Chow. “Sport technology consumers: Segmenting users of sports wearable devices based on technology readiness”. In: *Computers in Human Behavior* 84 (2018), pp. 320–330. DOI: 10.1016/j.chb.2018.02.031.
- [34] Ali Kuru. “Exploring Experience of Runners with Sports Tracking Technology”. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing*. ACM. 2016, pp. 113–124. DOI: 10.1145/2971648.2971741.
- [35] George Lakoff and Mark Johnson. *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press, 1980.
- [36] Alan M. Lane et al. “The Effects of Music Tempo and Genre on Performance in a 16.1-km Running Time Trial”. In: *Psychology of Sport and Exercise* 43 (2019), pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1016/j.psychsport.2019.03.004.

- [37] Shih-Yang Lin et al. “Pub-Point Upon Body: Exploring Eyes-Free Interaction and Methods on an Arm”. In: *Proceedings of the 24th annual ACM symposium on User interface software and technology*. ACM, 2011, pp. 481–488. DOI: 10.1145/2047196.2047244.
- [38] Karon E. MacLean. “Haptics: Touch feedback in human-computer interaction”. In: *Springer Handbook of Robotics*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2008, pp. 719–739.
- [39] Dave Maertens. “Why people use running apps: A study based on the uses and gratifications theory”. Masterproef. UNIVERSITEIT GENT FACULTEIT ECONOMIE EN BEDRIJFSKUNDE, 2014.
- [40] Fábio S. Magalhães et al. “The Use of Haptic Guidance for Improving Front Crawl Swimming Technique”. In: *Sports Biomechanics* 15.2 (2016), pp. 186–200.
- [41] Daphne Menheere et al. “The Runner’s Journey: Identifying Design Opportunities for Running Motivation Technology”. In: *Proceedings of the 11th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction: Shaping Experiences, Shaping Society*. NordiCHI ’20. Tallinn, Estonia, 2020, pp. 1–14. DOI: 10.1145/3419249.3420151.
- [42] Pavlo Molchanov et al. “Hand Gesture Recognition with 3D Convolutional Neural Networks”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops* (2015). DOI: 10.1109/CVPRW.2015.7301347.
- [43] Andreas C Mühlbacher and Billy Sperlich. “Movement Matters! How Interacting With Wearable Devices While Running Affects Running Movement”. In: *Frontiers in Psychology* 11 (2020), p. 580404. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.580404.
- [44] Donald A. Norman and Stephen W. Draper. *User-Centered System Design: New Perspectives on Human-Computer Interaction*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc., 1986. ISBN: 9780898598728.
- [45] Vincenzo Patania et al. “The Psychophysiological Effects of Different Tempo Music on Endurance Versus High-Intensity Performances”. In: *Frontiers in Psychology* 11 (2020), p. 74. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00074.
- [46] Carol Pinchefsky. “The best running apps in 2024, tested by our editors”. In: *CNN Underscored* (2024). URL: <https://www.cnn.com/underscored/cnn-underscored-reviews/running-apps>.
- [47] Matthew Rebold et al. “The relationship between cell phone use, physical and sedentary activity in college students”. In: *Journal of Behavioral Addictions* 2.4 (2013), pp. 274–282. DOI: 10.1556/JBA.2.2013.4.4.
- [48] Saule Saulyanas, Catherine S. Fichten, and Jane Gledhill. “How and Why We Run: Investigating the Experiences of Blind and Visually-Impaired Runners”. In: *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. CHI ’21. Yokohama, Japan: Association for Computing Machinery, 2021. ISBN: 9781450380959. DOI: 10.1145/3411764.3445525. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445525>.

- [49] Christoph Schaffert, Andrea Schättin, and Jochen Kämpf. “The effects of visual and auditory real-time feedback on surfing performance”. In: *Frontiers in psychology* 10 (2019), p. 1426. DOI: 0.3389/fpsyg.2019.01426.
- [50] Linda Schücker, Lena Schmeing, and Norbert Hagemann. ““Look around while running!” Attentional focus effects in inexperienced runners”. In: *Psychology of Sport and Exercise* 27 (2016), pp. 205–212. DOI: 10.1016/j.psychsport.2016.08.013.
- [51] Magdalena Seuter et al. “Running with Technology: Evaluating the Impact of Interacting with Wearable Devices on Running”. In: *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 1.3 (2017), pp. 1–17. DOI: 10.1145/3132272.3134130.
- [52] Anabela G. Silva et al. “Effectiveness of Mobile Applications Running on Smartphones to Promote Physical Activity: A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis”. In: *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17.7 (2020), p. 2251. DOI: 10.3390/ijerph17072251.
- [53] Dinesh Srinivasan and Jinsheng Chen. “Wearable haptic systems for gait rehabilitation: A review”. In: *Journal of neuroengineering and rehabilitation* 16.1 (2019), pp. 1–23.
- [54] Statista. *Number of smartphone users worldwide from 2016 to 2021*. <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1143723/smartphone-users-in-the-world>. Accessed on 2023-11-16. 2018.
- [55] Statista Research Department. *Use of phone/app for running related activities in the U.S. 2017*. 2022. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/886221/use-of-phone-app-for-running-related-activities-usa/>.
- [56] Suraj Suryawanshi. “Flutter Clean Architecture MVVM”. In: *Medium* (2020). URL: <https://medium.com/@codemax120/flutter-clean-architecture-mvvm-f8802e3df564>.
- [57] Anna Szabó, Dömötör Németh, and Áron Lázár. “The Effects of Binaural Beats on Cognitive Flexibility: A Pilot Study”. In: *Journal of Cognitive Enhancement* 3.4 (2019), pp. 393–401. DOI: 10.1007/s11572-019-09516-2.
- [58] Jenifer Tidwell. *Designing Interfaces: Patterns for Effective Interaction Design*. O’Reilly Media, 2010. ISBN: 9780596155094.
- [59] Bas Van Hooren, Guy Plasqui, and Kenneth Meijer. “The Effect of Wearable-Based Real-Time Feedback on Running Injuries and Running Performance: A Randomized Controlled Trial”. In: *The American Journal of Sports Medicine* 52.3 (2024), pp. 754–764. DOI: 10.1177/03635465231222464.
- [60] Bas Van Hooren et al. “Real-Time Feedback by Wearables in Running: Current Approaches, Challenges and Suggestions for Improvements”. In: *Journal of Sports Sciences* 38.2 (2020), pp. 214–230. DOI: 10.1080/02640414.2019.1661816.
- [61] Steven Vos et al. “From problem to solution: Developing a personalized smartphone application for recreational runners following a three-step design approach”. In: *Procedia engineering* 147 (2016), pp. 799–805. DOI: 10.1016/j.proeng.2016.08.403.

- [62] D. Wang et al. “Effectiveness of haptic feedback in improving motor task performance in physical activities”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Haptics* 12.3 (2019), pp. 312–320.
- [63] Gertjan Wijnalda et al. “PAMS: a personalized affective music system for sports activities”. In: *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval*. 2005, pp. 463–470.
- [64] Daniel Williams et al. “The Effects of Music on Performance and Perceived Effort in Trail Runners Using Sensor Control to Generate Biosynchronous Music”. In: *Sensors* 20.13 (2020), p. 4528. DOI: 10.3390/s20134528.
- [65] Margaret Wilson. “Six Views of Embodied Cognition”. In: *Psychonomic Bulletin Review* 9.4 (2002), pp. 625–636.
- [66] Kim A Witte et al. “Vibrotactile feedback improves running form”. In: *Scientific Reports* 10.1 (2020), pp. 1–9. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-61491-8.
- [67] Paweł Wozniak et al. “RUFUS: Remote Supporter Feedback for Long Distance Runners”. In: *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM. 2015, pp. 3535–3544. DOI: 10.1145/2702123.2702581.

Appendices

A Archived Websites

Software Documentation:

- Google. Firebase documentation. <https://firebase.google.com/docs>. Accessed: 2023-07-02. 2023.
- Google. Flutter documentation. <https://docs.flutter.dev/>. Accessed: 2023-07-02. 2023.
- Mehmet Fatih Simsek. just audio: A Flutter audio plugin. https://pub.dev/packages/just_audio. Accessed: 2023-07-02. 2023.

Statistical Data:

- Statista. Number of smartphone users worldwide from 2016 to 2021. <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1143723/smartphone-users-in-the-world>. Accessed on 2023-11-16. 2018.
- Statista Research Department. Number of smartphone users worldwide from 2016 to 2021 (in billions). 2018. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/330695/number-of-smartphone-users-worldwide/>.
- Statista Research Department. Use of phone/app for running related activities in the U.S. 2017. 2022. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/886221/use-of-phone-app-for-running-related-activities-usa/>.

B Design Recommendations for Run and Interact 2.0 App

This appendix includes additional design recommendations for the "Breathe and Run 02" app. Some of the design recommendations described below are detailed in the **Design Suggestions** section of the thesis, while the complete design concepts are presented here for the reader's reference. Each design screen is accompanied by a brief description, summarizing its function and relevance to the overall project.

1 **Landing page:** Introduces the app's concept with some illustrations. Offers a 7-day free trial for app enjoyment.

2 **Welcome Screen:** Offers options to sign up, log in, or continue with Apple, Google, or other social media accounts.

3 **Get Started Screen:** This feature allows users to quickly start a run with their previously saved settings.

4 **Guided Breathing Patterns (Version 01):** Displays some specific guided breathing patterns with instructions on inhale, hold, and exhale durations.

5 **Personalized Breathing Guidance Screen:** Provides a prompt to start a new session for personalized guidance.

6 **Inhale/Exhale Duration Customization:** Allows users to customize inhale and exhale durations using sliders.

7 **Settings Screen:** Offers options to adjust auditory cue volume and type, and to connect a heart rate monitor.

8 **Run Screen:** Displays real-time data during the run, including pace, distance, time, and heart rate, along with the current breathing instruction. Also includes buttons for music control and accessing the user profile.

Figure 17: Illustrating the home screen and run screen of the Breathe and Run app.

1 **Personalized Breathing Guidance Screen:** This is the main screen where users can choose their preferred breathing pattern, customize it if needed, and select an auditory feedback style. It also displays a button for a Quick Start run.

2 **App recommendations for popular and new running programs:** This is the main screen where users can review and choose from the app's offered or user-recommended running and breathing patterns.

3 **Guided Breathing Patterns (Version 02):** Displays some specific guided breathing patterns, including instructions on inhale, hold, and exhale durations. Additionally, the user has the option to select the style of auditory feedback.

4 **Run Screen:** The screen does show real-time data during the run, including distance, pace, time, and heart rate. Additionally, the "Save To Profile" button suggests the ability to save run data.

5 **Connect Your Wearable Screen:** This screen guides users through the process of connecting a heart rate monitor to the app. It offers instructions, device selection, connection status, and troubleshooting options.

6 **Connect Your Wearable (Advanced) Screen:** This screen offers advanced options for wearable integration, such as customizing the displayed data, setting heart rate zones, and accessing help resources for troubleshooting.

7 **Soundscapes Screen:** This screen allows users to select from pre-made running playlists (Morning, Evening) or create their own custom playlist.

8 **Run Summary Screen:** This screen presents a summary of the completed run, including distance, duration, pace, calories, average heart rate, breaths per minute, and steps per minute. It also offers the option to save the run data.

Figure 18: Illustrating the screens of Breathe and Run app.

1 **Welcome Screen:** Introduces the app's concept of personalized music selection for running. It offers options to connect various music streaming services for seamless integration.

2 **Connect to Spotify Screen:** This screen allows users to connect their Spotify account to the app, enabling access to their playlists and music library.

3 **Soundscapes Screen:** Displays different categories of pre-made playlists (Focus, Relax, Workout) and a search bar for finding specific soundscapes.

4 **Soundscape Details Screen:** Showcases a specific soundscape ("Lose Yourself in the Rainforest") with details like its type (Nature Sounds), a play button, and an option to adjust the volume.

5 **Guided Breathing Screen:** This screen provides a visual and auditory guide for a specific breathing pattern (4-step inhale). The clear instructions and visual cue help users maintain the correct rhythm for their breathing exercise while running. It also includes a "Start" and "Skip" button.

6 **Connect Your Wearable Screen:** This screen guides users through the process of connecting a wearable device (smartwatch or fitness tracker) to the app. It offers options to scan for devices, displays a list of compatible wearables, and shows real-time heart rate data.

7 **Most Popular Songs Screen:** This screen showcases a list of the most popular songs among app users, potentially categorized by genre or mood. It could include options to preview, add to a playlist, or start a run with the selected song.

8 **Customize Playlist Screen:** This screen allows users to create and edit their own playlists. They can name their playlist, add and reorder songs, and save their changes.

Figure 19: Illustrating the connection process with wearable devices and the data privacy screen of the Breathe and Run app.

Feedback Screen: This screen appears immediately after a run and allows users to rate their experience using a simple thumbs-up/thumbs-down system. It also prompts the user to categorize their feedback with options like "Too hard," "Just right," or "Too easy."

Post-Run Feedback Screen: This more detailed feedback screen asks users to share their thoughts on their recent run, including their satisfaction and usability ratings. There's space for a written comment and open-ended questions to gather qualitative feedback.

Progress Tracking Screen: This screen displays the user's progress in various metrics related to their breathing during runs. It includes average breaths per minute (BPM), consistency over time, and improvements in breathing rate. A graph visualizes the trends for easier understanding.

Error Screen: A generic error message screen informs users if the app encounters problems loading content. It suggests checking the internet connection or updating the app, and provides an option to report the problem.

Pair Devices Screen: This screen guides users through the process of connecting a heart rate monitor to the app. It provides step-by-step instructions, including turning on the monitor, selecting the device, and troubleshooting connection issues.

Figure 20: Illustrating potential user interface designs for feedback and error handling in the Breathe and Run app.